

Abstract

The homestay sector in Sri Lanka has experienced a steady rise in popularity, particularly within culturally rich regions like Kandy. However, there remains a research gap in understanding the specific factors that influence **traveller reservation intention**—particularly among **domestic visitors from Colombo**. This study aims to examine the influence of four key traveller preferences—**Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Amenities and Comfort, and Trust and Security**—on the **reservation intention** in the Kandy homestay industry.

A mono-method quantitative approach was adopted, using an online survey distributed to 316 respondents residing in **Colombo**. The survey instrument was developed through a structured operationalization of variables based on established literature, and the data was analysed using **SPSS**. Reliability and validity were tested using **Cronbach's Alpha** and the **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO)** measure. Factor analysis, correlation, and regression techniques were employed to assess relationships between independent and dependent variables.

Findings revealed that **all four independent variables** had a statistically significant **positive impact** on reservation intention, leading to the acceptance of all alternate hypotheses. Among them, **Amenities and Comfort** emerged as the most influential factor, while **Trust and Security** had the lowest impact. These insights offer practical implications for homestay operators and tourism strategists looking to align their offerings with traveller expectations and improve booking rates in Kandy's competitive hospitality landscape.

Keywords:

Reservation Intention, Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Amenities and Comfort, Trust and Security, Homestay Industry, Kandy, Traveller Preferences, Domestic Tourism, Sri Lanka

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Chapter 1

INTRODUCTION

Introduction to the Chapter

This chapter provides an introduction to the research, outlining the background, rationale, and problem statement of the study. The chapter also presents the aim and objectives of the research, along with the research questions and significance of the study. It sets the foundation for understanding the factors that influence reservation intentions in the homestay industry in Kandy, Sri Lanka, focusing particularly on travelers from Colombo. The chapter concludes with an explanation of the academic and practical significance of this study.

1.1 Background of the research

Tourism has become a significant economic contributor to Sri Lanka, with the country's diverse landscapes, rich history, and cultural heritage attracting both international and domestic tourists. Among the various accommodation options, **homestays** have become increasingly popular due to their ability to provide **authentic cultural experiences** at more affordable prices (Wickramasinghe et al., 2015). Homestays allow travelers to connect more intimately with local cultures, offering a more personal and immersive experience compared to traditional hotels.

In **Kandy**, Sri Lanka, a city known for its historical and cultural significance, the homestay sector has seen remarkable growth. The **Temple of the Tooth**, a UNESCO World Heritage site, along with traditional festivals like **Kandy Esala Perahera**, draw a wide range of tourists (Gunawardena, 2019). Despite the growing popularity of homestays in the region, there is a **lack of research** that specifically investigates the factors influencing **domestic travelers' decision-making** in choosing these accommodations, particularly tourists from **Colombo**.

Understanding the preferences and motivations of travelers is crucial for homestay owners, marketers, and tourism policymakers. Such insights can help enhance service offerings and improve marketing strategies to attract more visitors. This study aims to address this gap by exploring how **specific traveler preferences** impact **reservation intentions** in the homestay sector, focusing on **Colombo-based domestic tourists**.

1.1.1 Rationale for the Study

The rationale for this study arises from the increasing importance of the **homestay sector** in Sri Lanka's tourism industry, alongside the **lack of empirical research** on the preferences of **domestic travelers**, particularly those from **Colombo**. While homestays have great potential to provide **authentic cultural experiences** at affordable prices, there is limited understanding of how factors such as **price, location, comfort, and cultural immersion** influence travelers' decision to make a reservation (Wickramasinghe et al., 2015).

As the tourism industry in Sri Lanka continues to grow, it is crucial for **homestay owners and tourism marketers** to better understand the preferences and behaviors of domestic tourists, who may have different expectations compared to international visitors. Previous research has primarily focused on international tourists, neglecting the local market segment. Understanding domestic travelers' unique needs and preferences will help homestay businesses tailor their offerings, improving **customer satisfaction** and increasing **reservation rates** (Samarawickrama & Perera, 2017). This study aims to fill this gap by examining the factors influencing reservation intentions among **Colombo-based tourists**.

1.1.2 Area of Focus

This study concentrates on the **homestay industry in Kandy**, Sri Lanka, specifically examining **domestic travelers** from **Colombo**. The focus of the research is to explore the key factors influencing travelers' decisions to book homestays, which include:

- **Price Sensitivity:** The impact of affordability on accommodation choices, considering whether price is a determining factor for travelers when selecting homestays (Wickramasinghe et al., 2015).
- **Cultural Experiences:** The appeal of **cultural immersion** provided by homestays, which offer a unique way for travelers to engage with local culture and traditions (Gunawardena, 2019).
- **Location and Accessibility:** The role of **proximity to tourist attractions** and the convenience of **accessibility** in shaping booking intentions (Samarawickrama & Perera, 2017).
- **Amenities and Comfort:** The significance of basic comforts and amenities, such as clean facilities and reliable services, in the decision-making process for homestay bookings (Huang & Hsu, 2009).

By investigating these factors and their interrelationship with **reservation intentions**, this study aims to provide valuable insights into the preferences of **Colombo-based visitors**, helping homestay operators better cater to the domestic tourism market.

1.2 Problem Statement

The homestay sector in Kandy has seen considerable growth, yet there is insufficient understanding of the factors influencing the reservation decisions of domestic travelers, particularly those from Colombo. While international tourists have been studied extensively in the context of homestay preferences, there is limited research on how domestic travelers from Colombo, a key market for tourism, perceive and choose homestays. Without a clear understanding of these preferences, homestay owners and tourism stakeholders may struggle to meet the expectations of this important group of tourists.

Therefore, the problem this study seeks to address is: **How do traveler preferences influence the reservation intentions of domestic tourists, particularly from Colombo, when choosing homestays in Kandy, Sri Lanka?**

1.3 Aim, Objectives, and Research Questions

1.3.1 Aim

The aim of this research is to explore the impact of traveler preferences on reservation intentions in the homestay industry in Kandy, Sri Lanka, with a focus on domestic travelers from Colombo. This study seeks to identify the key factors that influence booking decisions and provide insights into how homestay owners can improve their offerings to attract more visitors.

1.3.2 Research Questions

The primary research questions guiding this study are:

- 1. What are the key factors that influence the reservation intentions of domestic travelers from Colombo when choosing homestays in Kandy?**
- 2. How do traveler preferences related to price, location, cultural experiences, and amenities affect the likelihood of reserving a homestay?**
- 3. Do the preferences of Colombo-based travelers differ from those of other domestic or international visitors to Kandy?**

1.3.3 Research Objectives

Primary Objective:

- To examine the impact of traveler preferences on reservation intentions for homestays in Kandy, focusing on visitors from Colombo.

Secondary Objectives:

1. To identify and analyze the key factors (e.g., price, location, cultural experiences, amenities) that influence domestic travelers' decision-making processes when choosing homestays.
2. To explore whether Colombo-based travelers exhibit distinct preferences compared to other domestic and international tourists visiting Kandy.
3. To assess the role of price sensitivity, cultural experiences, and other factors in shaping travelers' likelihood of reserving a homestay in Kandy.

1.4 Significance of the Study

Academic Significance

This study will contribute to the **limited literature on domestic tourism** in Sri Lanka, specifically regarding **homestay accommodations**. By focusing on **Colombo-based travelers**, it will provide valuable insights into local tourism behavior and fill the knowledge gap concerning **domestic tourists' preferences** in Sri Lanka. The findings will also enrich the broader **hospitality and tourism research** field by examining how **local cultural factors** impact accommodation choices, offering a deeper understanding of consumer behavior in the context of Sri Lanka's tourism industry (Wickramasinghe et al., 2015; Gunawardena, 2019).

Practical Significance

The practical implications of this research are significant for **homestay owners, tourism marketers, and policymakers** in Sri Lanka:

- **Homestay Owners:** The study will provide actionable recommendations to help homestay operators in **Kandy** tailor their services to better meet the needs of domestic travelers, thereby enhancing **customer satisfaction** and boosting **reservation rates** (Samarawickrama & Perera, 2017).
- **Tourism Marketers:** The findings will inform marketing strategies targeting domestic travelers from Colombo, aiding in the creation of **effective promotional campaigns** tailored to this market segment (Huang & Hsu, 2009).
- **Policymakers:** The research will contribute to the development of **policies promoting sustainable tourism**, supporting the growth of locally-owned homestays and benefiting the broader **Sri Lankan tourism economy** (Gunawardena, 2019).

1.5 Chapter Outline

Chapters	Description
Chapter 1	This chapter provides the reader with an overall introduction to the proposed study. Starting with the background of the subject and industry and the rationale in justifying the need for the research, the author covers areas such as area of focus, research aim and objectives. Furthermore, the significance, limitations and chapter categorization are also detailed in chapter 1.
Chapter 2	This chapter entails critical analysis of existing theories/models pertaining to the research area in subject, as well as literature review that uncovers and further explains each variable identified by the author, backed by past research articles, in determining factors influencing online grocery purchase intention. The chapter will also include key words and definitions relating to the topic.
Chapter 3	This chapter is allocated predominantly to detail the methodology used in conducting the research. The research design described by the research onion model is also illustrated along with sampling techniques, data collection, reliability and validity tests and ethical considerations. It further includes the conceptual framework and research hypotheses that will be tested later on.
Chapter 4	This chapter covers research data gathered and critically analyzed to provide clear and meaningful understanding of results. Demographic breakdowns, as well as SPSS derived data such as correlation matrix, regression analysis are included in this section. The chapter is also inclusive of testing hypotheses based on accumulated responses.
Chapter 5	The final chapter of the proposed study includes the overall conclusion, key findings from primary research as well as relevant recommendations and direction for future research.

Table 1: Chapter Outline

Source: Author Developed (2025)

1.6 Chapter Summary

This chapter introduced the research study on exploring the impact of traveler preferences on reservation intentions in the homestay industry in Kandy, Sri Lanka, specifically focusing on visitors from Colombo. It provided a comprehensive overview of the background of the study, emphasizing the significance of understanding the preferences of domestic travelers, particularly those from Colombo, who contribute significantly to the growth of the homestay sector.

The rationale for the study highlighted the gap in existing literature regarding domestic travelers' decision-making processes in choosing homestays, particularly in the context of Kandy, a popular tourist destination. The chapter outlined the research problem, which centers on how various factors such as price sensitivity, cultural experiences, location, and amenities influence the likelihood of reserving a homestay.

The research objectives were clearly stated, with the primary aim of examining the relationship between traveler preferences and reservation intentions. The chapter also presented the research questions that will guide the study and defined the academic and practical significance of the research, including its contribution to existing tourism literature and its potential impact on homestay owners, tourism marketers, and policymakers.

This chapter laid the foundation for the study, setting the stage for subsequent chapters, including the literature review, methodology, results, and recommendations. The detailed outline of the study's structure was provided to ensure clarity and coherence as the research progresses.

Chapter 2:

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Introduction to the Chapter

The purpose of this chapter is to provide a comprehensive review of the existing literature relevant to the study of traveler preferences and reservation intentions, specifically within the homestay industry. The chapter delves into several models and theories that explore the dynamics of customer behavior in hospitality, focusing on the key variables that influence reservation intentions. It also aims to critically analyze the relevant theoretical frameworks that help explain how travelers make decisions about booking accommodations, with particular reference to domestic tourists in Sri Lanka.

2.2 Dependent Variable

2.2.1 Reservation Intention

Reservation intention refers to the likelihood or intention of a customer to make a reservation for accommodation, such as a **homestay**. It is a critical measure of customer **decision-making behavior** in the **hospitality industry** and reflects a traveler's **cognitive process** and willingness to engage with a particular accommodation offering. Reservation intention is often considered a precursor to actual **booking behavior** and is influenced by a variety of personal preferences and external factors (Ajzen, 1991).

Reservation intention is regarded as a **dependent variable** because it is determined by several independent factors, including **perceived service quality**, **price**, **location**, **cultural experiences**, and individual preferences (Kim et al., 2009). Understanding reservation intentions is crucial for service providers as it enables them to predict customer behavior, personalize their offerings, and enhance customer satisfaction (Baker & Crompton, 2000).

In the tourism and hospitality context, research has increasingly focused on the key drivers that influence reservation intentions. While **external influences**, such as advertising and promotions, do play a role, **personal factors** like past experiences, satisfaction with similar services, and peer

recommendations often have a more substantial impact (Choi et al., 2016). Additionally, **value perceptions, convenience of the booking process, and the overall customer experience** are crucial in shaping reservation intentions (Jang & Feng, 2007).

In the case of **homestays**, these factors are further influenced by the **cultural and experiential aspects** of staying in a local home. Travelers often choose homestays for the authentic cultural immersion they offer, which traditional hotels cannot provide (Tussyadiah & Fesenmaier, 2009). Thus, understanding how these factors impact reservation intentions is especially relevant to this study.

2.3 Theoretical Framework

The **theoretical framework** of this study is built upon two widely recognized models: the **SERVQUAL Model** and **Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT)**. These models offer insights into how service quality, customer expectations, and satisfaction influence reservation intentions. Below is a detailed explanation of each of these frameworks.

2.3.1 SERVQUAL Model

The **SERVQUAL Model**, developed by **Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry** in the 1980s, is widely used to measure service quality across various industries, including hospitality. The model identifies five key dimensions that are critical to evaluating service quality:

- **Tangibles:** This dimension refers to the physical aspects of the service environment, such as the cleanliness of the homestay, the condition of the facilities, and the appearance of staff. The tangible aspects contribute significantly to the guest's initial impression and satisfaction (Parasuraman et al., 1985).
- **Reliability:** Reliability pertains to the service provider's ability to consistently perform the promised service dependably and accurately. In the context of homestays, this includes maintaining consistent cleanliness, hospitality, and service quality across all guest interactions (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000).
- **Responsiveness:** Responsiveness refers to the willingness of service providers to assist customers and provide prompt service. In a homestay, this could involve timely communication with potential guests, addressing inquiries efficiently, and resolving issues promptly (Parasuraman et al., 1985).
- **Assurance:** Assurance involves the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to instill confidence in customers. For homestays, this dimension includes the professionalism, friendliness, and the sense of security and comfort provided by the host (Zeithaml & Bitner, 2000).
- **Empathy:** Empathy reflects the personalized care and attention provided to customers. In a homestay, this could involve customized experiences, such as accommodating special

guest requests or offering tailored recommendations based on guest preferences (Parasuraman et al., 1985).

These dimensions are directly linked to customer satisfaction and play a significant role in influencing **reservation intentions**. When customers perceive high service quality across these dimensions, they are more likely to form positive expectations and make a reservation (Pizam & Ellis, 1999). The **SERVQUAL model** allows homestay operators to assess their service performance, identify areas for improvement, and ultimately enhance customer satisfaction, leading to increased reservation intentions.

Figure 1: Measuring Service Quality Using SERVQUAL Model

Source: (ReserachGate.2024)

2.3.2 Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT)

The **Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT)** was developed by Richard L. Oliver in 1980. This theory posits that consumer satisfaction and future behavioral intentions (e.g., intention to

make a reservation) are influenced by the confirmation or disconfirmation of pre-purchase expectations. ECT operates on the principle that customers have expectations before they experience a service, and these expectations are either confirmed or disconfirmed based on their actual service experience.

- **Pre-purchase expectations:** These are the beliefs or assumptions that travelers form about a homestay before actually staying there. Expectations are often shaped by advertising, reviews, recommendations, or previous experiences.
- **Perceived performance:** This refers to the actual experience that a traveler has when staying at the homestay. It includes the perceived quality of service, comfort, and overall satisfaction during the stay.
- **Confirmation/Disconfirmation:** If the perceived performance meets or exceeds expectations, customers experience **confirmation**, leading to higher satisfaction. If the perceived performance falls short of expectations, customers experience **disconfirmation**, leading to dissatisfaction.
- **Satisfaction:** ECT suggests that satisfaction is the result of the confirmation of expectations. Higher satisfaction is likely to result in greater future behavioral intentions, including the intention to make future reservations.

ECT is highly relevant for understanding traveler behavior because homestays rely heavily on personal expectations of the experience. The more a homestay can meet or exceed a traveler’s expectations, the more likely they are to return or recommend the homestay to others, increasing future reservation intentions.

Figure 2: ECT- based-IS-Continuance Model-

Source: (Bhattacharjee 2004; Liao et al. 2009; Limayem et al. 2007; Limayem & Cheung 2008)

2.4 Critical Analysis of Models and Theories

To gain a deeper understanding of the factors influencing **reservation intentions** in the **homestay industry**, it is crucial to critically evaluate the **theoretical models and frameworks** commonly used in **hospitality and tourism research**. Two widely recognized frameworks in the literature on **customer satisfaction** and **service quality** are the **SERVQUAL Model** and **Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT)**. Both models provide valuable insights into how travelers perceive **service quality** and make decisions regarding their **accommodation choices**.

However, despite their broad application, both models have limitations, particularly when applied to the unique **homestay context**, which is inherently more personal, culturally immersive, and experiential than traditional hospitality services. The **SERVQUAL Model**, while highly effective in evaluating general service quality across industries, may not fully capture the nuances of the **personalized experiences** offered by homestays, such as the **cultural exchange** and **local interactions** that are central to this type of accommodation (Parasuraman et al., 1985). Similarly, **Expectation-Confirmation Theory (ECT)**, which posits that satisfaction is based on the comparison of **pre-purchase expectations** and **post-purchase perceptions**, may overlook the dynamic nature of cultural and social influences in the homestay sector (Oliver, 1980).

Despite these limitations, both models offer valuable insights into the relationship between **service quality**, **customer expectations**, and **reservation intentions**. A critical evaluation of these frameworks, particularly in the context of **homestays in Sri Lanka**, can help refine their applicability and identify additional factors that influence reservation behavior, such as **local cultural immersion**, **personalized services**, and **cultural perceptions** (Huang & Hsu, 2009).

2.5 Factors Influencing Reservation Intentions

1. Price Sensitivity

Price sensitivity remains one of the most significant factors influencing reservation intentions, particularly in markets where consumers have limited discretionary income, as is often the case for domestic travelers. Numerous studies have shown that price plays a vital role in shaping consumer choices, particularly for those seeking more affordable accommodation options (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

- **Price-Quality Perception:** Travelers tend to weigh the price against the perceived quality of the service they are receiving. For example, a study by Choi, Heo, and Law (2016) found that travelers who perceive a homestay to provide a good price-to-quality ratio are more likely to book accommodations, particularly if the homestay provides cultural immersion or local experiences. Domestic travelers from Colombo, seeking affordable yet authentic experiences, are likely to make decisions based on perceived value for money.
- **Price Discounts and Offers:** Special promotions or seasonal discounts also have a significant impact on reservation intentions. According to Nisar, Prabhakar, and Gupta (2020), travelers are more inclined to make a reservation if they perceive they are receiving a good deal, especially during peak tourist seasons. Offering discounts or free additional services (such as breakfast or guided local tours) can further enhance the appeal of homestays and increase booking rates.

As highlighted by Li, Liu, and Zhang (2021), price sensitivity also influences decision-making in the tourism industry, with travelers often adjusting their expectations and choices depending on the affordability of the accommodation. In Kandy, domestic travelers might opt for homestays over hotels, primarily because of lower rates, especially in comparison to international travelers who might prioritize other factors such as amenities or luxury.

2. Location and Accessibility

Location is often cited as one of the most critical factors in decision-making, as travelers generally prefer accommodations that provide convenience and access to major tourist attractions. This is particularly true in destinations like Kandy, where visitors are primarily motivated by the desire to explore historical and cultural landmarks.

- **Proximity to Attractions:** According to Gartner (2008), travelers often prioritize accommodation that provides easy access to major tourist sites. In Kandy, attractions such as the Temple of the Tooth, the Royal Botanical Gardens, and Kandy Lake are key draws for visitors. Homestays located near these attractions are more likely to be chosen due to the convenience they offer. For domestic travelers from Colombo, who may visit

Kandy for short trips, the proximity to these sites significantly enhances the appeal of homestays.

- **Transportation Links:** Accessibility by public transportation is another important factor. Domestic travelers may not always have access to private transportation, so homestays located near major transportation hubs or with easy access to bus or train services are more likely to attract bookings (Dwyer et al., 2010). Kandy's relatively compact layout means that easy access to local buses or taxis can enhance the attractiveness of homestays to domestic tourists.
- **Scenic Environment:** The natural beauty of Kandy, with its surrounding hills and lakes, is another factor that influences reservation intentions. Studies show that tourists prefer accommodations that offer scenic views or are located in areas of natural beauty (Weiler & Walker, 2015). Homestays in Kandy that provide stunning views of the surrounding landscape or are located in tranquil, natural settings may have a distinct advantage in attracting reservations from travelers seeking a peaceful, nature-oriented experience.

4. Amenities and Comfort

While homestays are primarily known for their cultural immersion, **comfort** and **amenities** remain essential in influencing reservation intentions. Travelers still expect a minimum level of comfort and convenience, even when seeking alternative forms of accommodation like homestays.

- **Basic Comforts:** Research by Kivela and Chu (2001) shows that factors like cleanliness, comfort, and basic amenities (such as hot water, clean beds, and Wi-Fi) are crucial in determining overall satisfaction and reservation intentions. Travelers from Colombo, accustomed to certain comfort levels in hotels, are likely to have specific expectations regarding the comfort of their accommodations. If these expectations are not met, they may be less likely to reserve a homestay in Kandy.
- **Additional Services:** Providing additional services such as home-cooked meals, guided tours, or other local experiences can add considerable value to a homestay. As noted by Tussyadiah and Fesenmaier (2009), travelers often seek added value beyond basic accommodation, and homestays that offer such personalized services are more likely to increase reservation intentions.
- **Technology and Modern Conveniences:** The incorporation of modern technologies such as high-speed internet, USB charging stations, and smart TVs has become increasingly important, especially for younger travelers. Research by Stokburger-Sauer, Teichmann, and Reisinger (2012) found that technological convenience plays a significant role in travelers' accommodation choices, even in non-traditional settings like homestays.

6. Trust and Security

Finally, **trust and security** are essential for travelers when booking accommodations. Homestays, by nature, require a higher degree of trust than traditional hotels, as guests are staying in private homes and interacting with hosts.

- **Trust in the Host:** A study by Susskind et al. (2003) emphasized that trust in the service provider (in this case, the homestay host) is a critical factor influencing reservation intentions. Guests must feel comfortable with the host, and the host must convey trustworthiness through clear communication and professional behavior.
- **Perceived Safety:** Safety is a top concern for many travelers, and ensuring that the homestay is in a safe neighborhood with secure facilities is crucial. As noted by Jennings and Weiler (2006), travelers are more likely to book accommodations where they feel their personal safety and the security of their belongings are assured.
- **Clear Communication and Transparency:** Trust is built through transparency in the booking process and clear communication about the accommodations, amenities, and house rules. According to McKinsey (2019), travelers appreciate when hosts are upfront about any additional charges or policies and provide clear and accurate descriptions of what to expect.

2.6 Chapter Summary

This section has highlighted the various factors influencing reservation intentions in the homestay industry. These factors include **price sensitivity, cultural immersion, location and accessibility, comfort and amenities, reviews and recommendations, and trust and security**. Each of these factors plays a significant role in the decision-making process of domestic travelers, particularly in Kandy, Sri Lanka. By understanding these factors, homestay operators can better tailor their services to meet the needs of potential guests, thereby increasing their chances of securing reservations.

Chapter 03

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK AND RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Introduction

This chapter outlines the research methodology and conceptual framework used in this study to investigate the impact of traveler preferences on reservation intentions in the homestay industry in Kandy, Sri Lanka. The chapter begins with an explanation of the conceptual framework that underpins the research, followed by the development of hypotheses based on the variables identified in the literature review. The key definitions of these variables are provided to ensure clarity, followed by the operationalization process and the corresponding measurement scales used in the study.

3.2 Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework is designed to visualize the relationship between various independent and dependent variables that affect reservation intentions in the homestay industry. The framework provides a systematic way of understanding how traveler preferences influence their decision to reserve a homestay in Kandy, Sri Lanka.

Figure 3.1: Conceptual Framework Source : Author Developed (2025)

This conceptual framework helps establish the relationships between these variables, allowing the researcher to test how each factor influences travelers' reservation intentions.

Key Elements of the Framework:

- **Independent Variables:**
 - **Price Sensitivity:** Travelers' willingness to pay based on perceived value for money (Choi, Heo, & Law, 2016).
 - **Location and Accessibility:** Proximity to key tourist attractions and transportation options (Gartner, 2008).
 - **Amenities and Comfort:** The basic services and conveniences expected by travelers (Kivela & Chu, 2001).
 - **Trust and Security:** Confidence in the safety and reliability of the host and accommodation (Susskind et al., 2003).

Dependent Variable:

- **Reservation Intention:** The likelihood that a traveler will make a reservation based on the influence of the above factors (Kotler & Keller, 2016).

3.3 Hypothesis Development

Based on the literature review and the identified variables in the conceptual framework, the following hypotheses are developed for the research:

- | | |
|-----------------------|--|
| Hypothesis 1 → | H1: Price sensitivity has a significant negative impact on reservation intention in the homestay industry in Kandy. |
| Hypothesis 2 → | H2: Location and accessibility have a significant positive impact on reservation intention in the homestay industry in Kandy. |
| Hypothesis 3 → | H3: The availability of amenities and comfort has a significant positive impact on reservation intention in the homestay industry in Kandy. |
| Hypothesis 4 → | H4: Trust and security have a significant positive impact on reservation intention in the homestay industry in Kandy. |

3.4 Key Definitions of Variables

Dependent Variable

Reservation Intention

Reservation intention refers to the traveller's conscious willingness and likelihood to book a homestay accommodation based on various influencing factors. It reflects the behavioral intention of potential customers to make a reservation, especially when prompted by specific attributes such as price, safety, comfort, and location. Adapted from Ajzen's Theory of Planned Behavior (1991), which posits that behavioral intentions are predictive of actual behavior

Independent Variables

Price Sensitivity

Dodds, Monroe, and Grewal (1991) suggest that perceived value and price have a significant influence on purchase intention, especially in service-related contexts such as tourism. Price sensitivity is the degree to which a change in the price of homestay accommodations influences the traveller's intention to reserve. A highly price-sensitive traveller is more likely to compare alternatives and choose based on affordability.

Safety and Security

Maslow's hierarchy of needs emphasizes safety as a fundamental motivator for human behavior, which has been extended to hospitality and travel studies (Rittichainuwat & Chakraborty, 2009). This factor reflects the traveller's perception of physical and digital security at the homestay property. It includes aspects such as secure payment systems, privacy, personal safety, trust in the host, and overall assurance while staying at the location.

Amenities and Comfort

According to Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry's SERVQUAL model (1988), tangible elements such as facilities and physical environment influence customer satisfaction and intent. Amenities and comfort refer to the perceived quality and availability of facilities offered at the homestay (e.g., cleanliness, Wi-Fi, air conditioning, kitchen access, room size, and bed comfort). These attributes contribute to the overall convenience and satisfaction of the traveller.

Location and Accessibility

Chen and Tsai (2007) emphasized the role of location in influencing destination loyalty and traveller behavior in hospitality research. Location and accessibility capture the importance of the homestay's proximity to transport links, tourist attractions, and urban convenience. It includes ease of reaching the property, neighborhood safety, and walkability or road access.

3.5 Operationalization of Variables

Concept	Variable	Indicators	Sources	Measurement	Question No. Section B
Exploring the Impact of Traveller Preference on Reservation Intentions in the Homestay Industry in Kandy: With Special Reference to Visitors from Colombo, Sri Lanka”	DEPENDENT VARIABLE				
	Reservation Intention	Likelihood of Reserving	Ajzen, I. (1991) Kim, J. H., & Lee, H. J. (2014)	Likert Scale	1
		Repeat Booking Intentions	Baker, D. A., & Crompton, J. L. (2000) Morrison, A. M., & O'Leary, J. T. (2004)	Likert Scale	2
		Time Spent on Platforms	Tussyadiah, I. P., & Fesenmaier, D. R. (2009) Beldona, S., & Aysu, B. (2015)	Likert Scale	3
		Intention to Recommend	Oliver, R. L. (1999) Zeithaml, V. A., Parasuraman, (1990)	Likert Scale	4
	INDEPENDENT VARIABLES				
	Price Sensitivity	Willingness to Pay for Homestays	Kotler & Keller (2016) Nisar, T. M. Prabhakar, G. & Gupta, A. (2020) hoi, S., Heo, C., & Law, R. (2016)	Likert Scale	5
		Price Comparison with Other Types of Accommodation	Choi, S., Heo, C., & Law, R. (2016) Baker, D. A., & Crompton, J. L. (2000)	Likert Scale	6
		Importance of Price in Booking Decision	Susskind et al. (2003) Kotler & Keller (2016)	Likert Scale	7
		Preference for Budget-Friendly Options	Nisar, T. M. Prabhakar, G. S. & Gupta, A. (2020)	Likert Scale	8
		Response to Discounts and Promotions	Baker, D. A., & Crompton, J. L. (2000) Kotler & Keller (2016)	Likert Scale	9

Concept	Variable	Indicators	Sources	Measurement	Question No. Section B
	Cultural Experience and Immersion	Preference for cultural experiences	Tussyadiah, Wang, & Jung (2017)	Likert Scale	10
		Value placed on cultural immersion	McKercher & du Cros (2002)	Likert Scale	11
	Location and Accessibility	Proximity to key tourist spots	Gartner (2008) Li, Liu, & Zhang (2021)	Likert Scale	12
		Ease of access to public transport or private shuttles	Li, Liu, & Zhang (2021)	Likert Scale	13
	Amenities and Comfort	Cleanliness and room quality	Kivela & Chu (2001)	Likert Scale	14
		Availability of essential amenities (Wi-Fi, hot water)	Stokburger-Sauer, Teichmann, & Reisinger (2012)	Likert Scale	15
	Reviews and Recommendations	Importance of online reviews	Cheung et al. (2009)	Likert Scale	16
		Influence of family/friend recommendations	Liu & Park (2015)	Likert Scale	17
	Trust and Security	Trust in the host's honesty	Susskind et al. (2003)	Likert Scale	18
		Perceived safety of the homestay location	Jennings & Weiler (2006)	Likert Scale	19

Table 2: Operationalization of Variables

Source: Author developed (2025)

3.6 Methodology

The **research design** refers to the overall strategy and framework that directs the collection, analysis, and interpretation of data. It serves as a blueprint for addressing the research questions, ensuring methodological rigor, and providing a clear pathway to achieving the study's objectives. The choice of research design is critical, as it significantly impacts the **validity, reliability, and generalizability** of the results (Creswell, 2014).

Figure 4: Research Onion Model Source:Saunders et al (2009)

3.6.1 Research Philosophy

The **positivist philosophy** is the most suitable choice for this study on **reservation intentions** in the **homestay industry** in **Kandy, Sri Lanka**. Positivism is grounded in the belief that knowledge is derived from observable and measurable phenomena, emphasizing **scientific verification, logical reasoning, and mathematical proof** to draw conclusions (Saunders et al., 2016). This approach is ideal for **quantitative research**, where **hypotheses** are tested using

empirical data, allowing for clear and reliable insights into the factors influencing travelers' reservation intentions.

In this study, the researcher will test **hypotheses** based on established theories such as the **Theory of Planned Behavior** and the **Expectation-Confirmation Theory** (Ajzen, 1991; Oliver, 1980). Positivism supports the use of structured surveys with closed-ended questions, which can generate **quantifiable data** that can be **statistically analyzed**. This allows for objective measurement of variables like **price sensitivity, cultural immersion, trust, and location**, all of which influence reservation intentions (Kim et al., 2009; Tussyadiah & Fesenmaier, 2009).

Positivism is also aligned with the **deductive approach**, where hypotheses are formulated and tested through empirical data. The use of a structured survey ensures the **reliability** and **replicability** of the findings, while minimizing potential researcher bias. This methodology enables the study to produce **generalizable results**, offering valuable insights for **homestay operators, policymakers, and researchers** in the **tourism sector**.

In conclusion, the **positivist approach** ensures that the study maintains **objectivity**, tests established theories, and generates **evidence-based** insights into the factors affecting **reservation intentions** in the **homestay market**.

3.6.2 Research Approach

The **deductive approach** is chosen for this study on reservation intentions in the homestay industry in Kandy, Sri Lanka, as it aligns with the **positivist philosophy**. The deductive approach begins with established theories, such as the **Theory of Planned Behavior** and the **Expectation-Confirmation Theory**, to develop hypotheses. Data is then collected and analyzed to test these hypotheses, aiming to determine whether the proposed relationships hold true in the specific context of homestay bookings.

This approach is appropriate because it allows for **systematic testing** of existing theories using **quantitative data**, ensuring objectivity and reducing bias. The hypotheses will guide the survey design, focusing on measurable variables like **price sensitivity, cultural immersion, and trust**. The research employs structured surveys and statistical analysis, making the study **generalizable** to a broader population of domestic travelers. Overall, the deductive approach provides a clear, structured framework for testing hypotheses and contributing empirical evidence to the field of tourism and hospitality.

3.5.3 Research Strategy

In this study on **reservation intentions in the homestay industry in Kandy**, the **research strategy** is centered around the **survey method**, a commonly used technique in quantitative research. According to Saunders et al. (2007), a research strategy outlines the plans and procedures by which a researcher expects to carry out the study. Surveys are particularly effective when the research requires the

collection of data from a large sample, making them an ideal choice for this study, which seeks to measure the factors influencing reservation intentions across a broad group of domestic travelers.

Surveys are advantageous in that they allow the researcher to collect data from a representative sample of the population, providing a broad overview of the attitudes, preferences, and behaviors of travelers. The data collected through surveys can then be analyzed statistically, offering insights that can be generalized to a larger population. This strategy is particularly useful in testing hypotheses derived from existing theories, which aligns with the **deductive approach** of the study.

The **survey strategy** involves the use of **structured questionnaires** with predetermined questions, which is an efficient and cost-effective way of gathering data. By using closed-ended questions, such as Likert-scale items, respondents are asked to indicate their level of agreement or preference, providing quantifiable data that can be easily analyzed. This structured approach minimizes the risk of researcher bias, ensuring the objectivity and reliability of the findings.

The survey method is not only cost-effective but also allows for the collection of large amounts of data in a relatively short period. Additionally, surveys provide the flexibility to target specific groups—in this case, domestic travelers from Colombo who are potential or actual customers of homestays in Kandy. This large-scale data collection supports the study's aim of generalizing findings to the broader population of travelers.

In conclusion, the **survey strategy** is the most appropriate research method for this study due to its efficiency, scalability, and alignment with the **deductive approach** and the **positivist philosophy**, ensuring the research remains objective, reliable, and able to draw generalizable conclusions.

3.5.4 Research Choice

The research choice refers to the method used for data collection, which can be mono, mixed, or multi-methods. **Mono-method** involves using a single data collection technique, while **mixed-methods** combines quantitative and qualitative methods, and **multi-method** involves using several methods within one study (Flick, 2011).

For this study, a **mono-method** approach will be employed, using **structured questionnaires** to gather data. The choice of a quantitative technique ensures a focused approach to collecting responses. Although **mixed-methods**, such as interviews, could provide additional depth, **time** and **financial constraints** have led to the adoption of surveys as the primary method. Future extensions of this study could explore the use of interviews to add further insights into the factors influencing **reservation intentions** in the homestay industry.

3.5.5 Time Horizon

The time horizon of a study can be **cross-sectional** or **longitudinal**, as outlined by Saunders et al. (2007). **Cross-sectional** studies collect data from a specific sample at a single point in time, while **longitudinal** studies track the same sample over an extended period, comparing changes over time. In cross-sectional studies, each survey collects data from a new sample, whereas longitudinal studies involve repeated measurements from the same individuals.

For this study on **reservation intentions** in the **homestay industry in Kandy**, a **cross-sectional** time horizon is adopted. Data will be collected from a sample that represents the broader population of domestic travelers at a particular point in time. Since the study aims to examine current behaviors and preferences, it will not focus on changes over time. This approach aligns with the study's goals and constraints regarding time and resources (Goddard & Melville, 2004).

3.5.6 Population and Sample Size of the Study

For this study on **reservation intentions** in the **homestay industry** in Kandy, the target population consists of **domestic travelers** from **Colombo**, Sri Lanka. Colombo is a key source of tourists for Kandy, which is reflective of the growth in regional tourism. According to the **Department of Census and Statistics (2021)**, Colombo is the most populous region in Sri Lanka, and domestic tourism is rising, particularly among young, tech-savvy individuals.

The **sample** for this study will focus on **domestic travelers** aged **20 to 45**, as this group is most likely to book accommodations online. According to recent studies by the **Sunday Observer (2020)**, this age range is divided into three key subgroups:

- **Young Travelers:** Aged 20-29
- **Middle-aged Travelers:** Aged 30-39
- **Settled Travelers:** Aged 40-45

The **total population** of Colombo is approximately **2,310,136** as of 2022 (PDHS Western Province, 2021), and data on travelers within these age groups will be used for primary research. The sample size will be determined based on the distribution of these groups within Colombo's population. This targeted demographic will provide valuable insights into the factors influencing reservation intentions within the homestay market.

Age Group	Population in Colombo District (2024)
20–29 years	920,382
30–39 years	919,624
40–49 years	791,588
Total	2,631,594

Table 3.2: Breakdown of Age Categories and Total Population for Primary Research

Source: (Macrotrends.net, 2025)

For statistical purposes, a sample size of **385 respondents** is required from the population of **domestic travelers in Colombo** within the age group **20-45 years** for this study on **reservation intentions** in the **homestay industry** in **Kandy**, Sri Lanka. This sample size ensures a **95% level of confidence** and a **5% margin of error** (Raosoft, 2025). The sample size calculation was determined using an **online sample calculator**, which is shown below:

What margin of error can you accept? 5% is a common choice	<input type="text" value="5"/> %
What confidence level do you need? Typical choices are 90%, 95%, or 99%	<input type="text" value="95"/> %
What is the population size? If you don't know, use 20000	<input type="text" value="2631594"/>
What is the response distribution? Leave this as 50%	<input type="text" value="50"/> %
Your recommended sample size is	385

Figure 5: Online Sample Calculator

Source: Raosoft, 2025

3.6.7 Sampling Technique and Choice Justification

Sampling techniques are broadly classified into **probability sampling** and **non-probability sampling**:

- **Probability Sampling**: Every individual in the target population has an equal chance of being included in the sample.
- **Non-probability Sampling**: The sample is chosen in an ad hoc manner, and there is no guarantee that every individual has an equal chance of inclusion.

For this study on **reservation intentions** in the **homestay industry in Kandy**, a **probability sampling technique**, specifically **stratified simple random sampling**, will be used. This method involves dividing the population into **homogeneous subgroups** based on key characteristics, such as age groups, and then selecting a random sample from each subgroup. In this research, the population will be divided into three age categories (20-29, 30-39, 40-45 years), with data collection targeted at these specific subgroups (Parsons, 2017).

Additionally, a **snowball sampling** technique, as recommended by Elfil and Negida (2017), will be employed due to the study's large sample size, limited time frame, and the online nature of the

target population. The researcher will distribute the survey to a few individuals within the targeted age categories, who will then share it with others in the same group, ensuring broad participation from domestic travelers in Colombo, who are engaged in online booking for homestays. Given these conditions, an **online survey** is the most suitable and efficient data collection method.

3.7 Pilot Study

Before the final research, a pilot study with 50 respondents was conducted to test the validity of the variables and gather feedback on potential improvements. Based on the positive feedback, no modifications were necessary, and the data collection process proceeded as planned

3.7.1 Reliability Measurement of the Variables

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.863	5

Figure 6: Reliability Statistics of Variables-Pilot Study

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The study focuses on four variables, including one dependent variable (reservation intention) and three independent variables (price sensitivity, location and accessibility, and amenities and comfort). The reliability of the questionnaire was assessed using **Cronbach's Alpha**. The overall reliability of all variables yielded a Cronbach's Alpha value of **0.863**, which exceeds the commonly accepted threshold of 0.65 (Achour, 2017), indicating that the questionnaire is sufficiently reliable for measuring the constructs in this study.

Cronbach's Alpha values above 0.8 are generally considered very good, while values exceeding 0.95 may indicate redundancy in the items (Taber, 2018). In addition, the reliability of each

individual variable was examined separately. All variables demonstrated Cronbach's Alpha values within the acceptable range, confirming that each construct is measured consistently and that the data collected from the survey is reliable. This ensures that the findings regarding the factors influencing reservation intentions in Kandy's homestay industry can be interpreted with confidence.

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Dependent	
Reservation Intention	0.851
Independent	
Price Sensitivity	0.631
Location and Accessibility	0.728
Trust and Security	0.983
Amenities and Comfort	0.962

Table 3: Reliability Of Statistics of Individual Variable-pilot Study

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

3.7.2 Validity Measurement of the Variables

To evaluate the suitability of the data for factor analysis in the context of this study on **reservation intentions for homestays in Kandy, Sri Lanka**, the **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Measure of Sampling Adequacy** and **Bartlett's Test of Sphericity** were conducted.

The **KMO value obtained was 0.892**, which is well above the commonly accepted threshold of 0.6, indicating a high degree of sampling adequacy and that the data is suitable for factor analysis (Kaiser, 1974). According to Hutcheson and Sofroniou (1999), a KMO value between 0.8 and 0.9 is considered "meritorious," suggesting that the variables share sufficient common variance.

Furthermore, the **Bartlett's Test of Sphericity** was highly significant (Chi-Square = 2932.574, **df = 190, p < 0.001**), supporting the presence of adequate correlations among the items and justifying the application of factor analysis (Bartlett, 1954). These results confirm the appropriateness of proceeding with exploratory factor analysis to identify underlying constructs among the independent and dependent variables of the study.

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.518
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	711.397
	df	190
	Sig.	.000

Table 4: Validity Measurement of Variables-Pilot Study

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

In this study, the **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure** was employed to evaluate the **sampling adequacy** of the dataset, while **Bartlett's Test of Sphericity** was used to examine the **strength of correlations among variables**, thereby confirming the suitability of the data for factor analysis.

For the variable "**Amenities and Comfort**", the KMO value was **0.813**, which, according to Kaiser (1974), falls within the "meritorious" range, indicating that the sampling adequacy is well above the minimum acceptable threshold of 0.6 (Field, 2013). Furthermore, **Bartlett's Test of Sphericity** yielded a statistically significant result ($\chi^2 = 460.565$, $df = 6$, $p < 0.001$), confirming that the correlation matrix is not an identity matrix and that the variables are sufficiently related for factor analysis.

These results support the validity of the measurement constructs used in the questionnaire and justify proceeding with further statistical analysis.

Variables	KMO Statistical Figures	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
		Chi-Square Approx	Degrees of Freedom	Significance
Reservation Intention	0.796	39.948	6	0.000
Price Sensitivity	0.769	105.848	6	0.000
Location and Accessibility	0.706	89.162	6	0.000
Trust and Security	0.829	202.757	6	0.000
Amenities and Comfort	0.802	162.856	6	0.000

Table 5: Validity Measurement (KMO Statistics, Bartlett's Data of Sphericity)-Pilot Study

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

3.8 Methods of Data Collection

Secondary data, including relevant publications, books, and existing theories, will be used to guide the research and develop pertinent hypotheses. To address the research questions, a well-structured survey will be designed, capturing the essential elements of the study. The questionnaire will utilize a **5-point Likert scale** in a multiple-choice format, ranging from **strongly agree** to **strongly disagree**. The survey will be distributed and administered online using the **JISC tool**, ensuring efficient data collection from domestic travelers in Colombo regarding their **reservation intentions** in the **homestay industry**.

3.9 Data Analysis and Tools

Accurate interpretation of research results is vital for maintaining data integrity. According to Shamoo and Resnik (2003), data analysis involves the systematic use of statistical tools to summarize, display, and assess data. For this study on **reservation intentions in the homestay industry in Kandy**, the **Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS)** will be employed to analyze the data.

To assess the reliability of the study, **Cronbach's Alpha** will be calculated. For measuring the validity and sample adequacy, **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO)** and **Bartlett's Test of Sphericity** will be used. Additionally, **regression** and **correlation tests** will evaluate the relationship between the independent variables (e.g., price sensitivity, cultural immersion) and the dependent variable (reservation intention). These statistical techniques will provide meaningful insights into

the factors influencing reservation intentions among domestic travelers from Colombo, ensuring a thorough and reliable analysis of the collected data.

3.9.1 Factor Analysis

Factor Analysis for Reservation Intention

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.768	69.204	69.204	2.768	69.204	69.204
2	.537	13.427	82.631			
3	.408	10.212	92.843			
4	.286	7.157	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 6:RI -Factor Analysis-Pilot Study

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Factor analysis was conducted to determine the underlying structure of the items measuring **reservation intention**. The **eigenvalue** represents the total variance explained by each principal component, and according to Kaiser’s criterion, components with eigenvalues greater than **1.0** are considered significant (UCLA, 2021).

As shown in the table above, **one principal component** has a eigenvalues above 1.0:

- **Component 1** has an eigenvalue of **2.768**, accounting for **69.204%** of the total variance.

Since that component exceed the threshold, it indicates that this factor sufficiently capture the majority of the variance in respondents’ reservation intention behavior. Therefore, the scale used to measure reservation intention demonstrates strong dimensionality and supports further inferential analysis.

Price Sensitivity (PS):

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.061	76.527	76.527	3.061	76.527	76.527
2	.788	19.704	96.231			
3	.104	2.591	98.822			
4	.047	1.178	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 7:PS- Factor Analysis-Pilot Study

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

According to **UCLA (2021)**, components with **eigenvalues greater than 1** are considered significant and retained for further analysis. In this analysis, only **Component 1** exceeds this threshold, with an eigenvalue of **3.061**, explaining **76.527%** of the total variance. This suggests that **a single factor strongly represents the construct of Price Sensitivity** in the dataset.

This high percentage of explained variance confirms that the items used to measure Price Sensitivity load heavily onto one component, indicating that the questions are consistent and measure the same underlying factor

Location and Accessibility (L&A):

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.803	70.064	70.064	2.803	70.064	70.064
2	1.002	25.049	95.113	1.002	25.049	95.113
3	.131	3.273	98.387			
4	.065	1.613	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 8: L&A- Factor Analysis-Pilot Study

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was conducted to examine the underlying structure of the variable *Location and Accessibility*. The total variance explained table indicates that two components recorded **eigenvalues greater than 1**, which is a commonly accepted threshold for factor retention as per Kaiser's criterion (UCLA, 2021).

- **Component 1** produced an eigenvalue of **2.803**, accounting for **70.064%** of the total variance.
- **Component 2** contributed an eigenvalue of **1.002**, adding an additional **25.049%**, leading to a **cumulative variance of 95.113%** explained by the two components.

This suggests that the items under this variable are well represented by two significant components, indicating strong construct validity. Since the cumulative variance is significantly high, the extracted components effectively summarize the variable's dimensionality.

Trust/Security (T/S)

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.820	95.495	95.495	3.820	95.495	95.495
2	.132	3.300	98.794			
3	.038	.939	99.733			
4	.011	.267	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 9:T/S- Factor Analysis-Pilot Study

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)** conducted to examine the structure of the “Trust and Security” variable indicates that the total variance is significantly explained by the first principal component.

- The **first component** yielded an **eigenvalue of 3.820**, which is well above the threshold of 1, indicating that this component meaningfully explains the data structure.
- This **first factor accounts for 95.495% of the total variance**, suggesting a very strong unidimensionality within the items measuring trust and security.
- All subsequent components have eigenvalues less than 1, which do not meet the criterion for retention, affirming that a **single factor solution is sufficient** for this construct.

This outcome strongly supports the **construct validity** of the Trust and Security dimension. The high explained variance suggests that the observed items are highly correlated and successfully measure a single underlying factor, thereby justifying the use of a **composite score** for further analysis such as regression or structural modeling.

Amenities and Comfort (AC):

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.606	90.145	90.145	3.606	90.145	90.145
2	.321	8.031	98.176			
3	.056	1.412	99.588			
4	.016	.412	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 10-AC Factor Analysis

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Factor analysis was conducted using Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to assess the underlying structure of the variable **Amenities and Comfort**. The **Total Variance Explained** table indicates that **one principal component** had an **eigenvalue greater than 1**, which is the commonly accepted threshold for significance (UCLA, 2021).

The first component recorded an eigenvalue of **3.606**, accounting for **90.145%** of the total variance. This indicates a very strong and dominant factor structure, suggesting that the items used to measure *Amenities and Comfort* are highly interrelated and load effectively onto a single factor.

Given that this component alone explains over 90% of the variance, it can be concluded that the construct of *Amenities and Comfort* is unidimensional and strongly supported by the data. This validates the appropriateness of the selected items for capturing the underlying concept within the context of the homestay industry in Kandy, Sri Lanka.

3.7 Ethical Considerations

In the execution of this research, the highest ethical standards were upheld throughout the study process. Prior to initiating data collection, ethical clearance was duly obtained by submitting the **Research Ethics and Integrity Risk Assessment Form** to the designated **Ethics Review Committee** at the affiliated academic institution. Data collection commenced only after receiving formal approval, ensuring adherence to institutional research protocols.

The research employed an online survey method using the university-approved **JISC** platform, which ensures secure data handling and minimizes risks associated with data privacy. Participants were provided with clear, written information outlining the purpose of the research, the nature of their involvement, and how the collected data would be analyzed and used strictly for **academic and non-commercial purposes**.

Participation was entirely voluntary, and **informed consent** was obtained prior to commencing the questionnaire. Respondents were assured that their **anonymity and confidentiality** would be preserved at all times. No personal identifiers were collected, and all responses were stored in encrypted formats to prevent unauthorized access. The results of the study were reported only in **aggregated form**, with no individual participant identifiable in any stage of analysis or reporting.

In line with academic best practices and data protection regulations, no personal data was disclosed to third parties. This approach supports full compliance with ethical principles surrounding **autonomy, privacy, informed consent, and data integrity**, thereby ensuring the credibility and trustworthiness of the study.

3.10 Chapter Summary

This chapter comprehensively outlined the methodological approach adopted for the research study on traveller preferences influencing reservation intentions in the homestay industry in Kandy. The research design was developed using the research onion framework, covering key elements such as the research philosophy, strategy, approach, data collection methods, and analysis techniques.

Following the literature review and conceptual framework, the chapter detailed the operationalization of key variables—including **Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Trust and Security, and Amenities and Comfort**—and introduced the **dependent variable: Reservation Intention**. A structured questionnaire was designed and pretested, and data were collected from a sample of respondents using an online survey.

The reliability of the constructs was assessed using **Cronbach's Alpha**, with all variables demonstrating acceptable to excellent internal consistency. Validity was established through the **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test** and **Bartlett's Test of Sphericity**, confirming the adequacy of the data for factor analysis. Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was then conducted to extract underlying factors, which supported the dimensional structure of the variables.

Finally, ethical considerations regarding informed consent, data confidentiality, and institutional research integrity were addressed. With the research design and tools validated, the study is now positioned for in-depth statistical analysis and hypothesis testing, which will be presented in the next chapter

Chapter 4

DATA PRESENTATION, DISCUSSION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

4.1 Introduction to the Chapter

This chapter presents, analyzes, and interprets the data collected for the study on how traveler preferences influence reservation intentions in the homestay sector in Kandy, Sri Lanka. The survey, distributed through the JISC platform, received a total of 323 responses. However, 7 responses were excluded due to incomplete data, resulting in a final sample size of 316 valid responses used for analysis.

The chapter begins with a demographic profile of the respondents, followed by a detailed examination of the variables through statistical techniques conducted in SPSS. Descriptive statistics, reliability and validity assessments, correlation matrices, and regression analyses are employed to evaluate the relationships among the variables. Additionally, the chapter includes hypothesis testing based on the survey data, providing meaningful insights through visual representations such as tables and charts. The results are interpreted in relation to the study objectives, offering a foundation for conclusions and recommendations in the subsequent chapter.

4.2 Survey Response Rate Calculation

Calculation

You distributed **385** questionnaires and received **248** valid responses.

The **response rate** is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Response Rate} = \left(\frac{\text{Number of Responses}}{\text{Number Distributed}} \right) \times 100$$

$$\text{Response Rate} = \left(\frac{248}{385} \right) \times 100 = 64.4\%$$

Out of the 385 questionnaires that were distributed through the university-endorsed JISC platform, a total of 248 valid responses were received. This results in a **response rate of 64.4%**, which is considered acceptable and statistically sound for academic research, particularly in the context of survey-based studies. A response rate above 60% suggests good participant

engagement, reduces the potential for non-response bias, and contributes to the reliability and generalizability of the study's findings. The collected data was deemed adequate for further quantitative analysis and provided a robust foundation for hypothesis testing and regression analysis in the subsequent chapters.

4.3 Sample Composition

The sample composition refers to the demographic and categorical breakdown of the final respondents who participated in the survey. A total of **385 questionnaires** were distributed, of which **248 completed responses** were received, yielding a **response rate of 64.4%**. This rate is considered acceptable for social science research, particularly when conducted through an online platform.

The study sample included participants residing primarily in **Colombo**, Sri Lanka—considered a key urban demographic with relevant exposure to travel, leisure, and homestay booking preferences. The target respondents were selected using **non-probability purposive sampling**, with a focus on individuals likely to have engaged with or considered homestay accommodations in Kandy.

Demographic profiling of the respondents reveals a balanced distribution across various categories including **age, gender, employment status, marital status, monthly income level, and travel frequency**. Notably, the **majority of respondents fell within the 30 to 39 age group**, categorized as “well-informed travellers,” which is particularly relevant given their higher tendency for digital interaction and online booking platforms. Gender representation was relatively balanced, and income levels largely clustered around the **Rs. 100,000 to Rs. 199,999** monthly bracket, indicating a middle- to upper-middle-income segment.

The **travel frequency** of the participants also provided important contextual relevance, with a significant portion reporting travel for leisure or personal reasons more than twice a year. This supports the study's focus on **reservation intention** within the homestay sector, as these individuals are more likely to be exposed to or consider alternative accommodation options such as homestays.

Thus, the final sample composition presents a robust and contextually relevant respondent base to analyze traveller preferences, perceptions, and their impact on reservation intentions in the Kandy homestay market.

4.4 Reliability Measurement of Variables

In this study, the reliability of the measurement instruments used in the survey was evaluated using **Cronbach's Alpha**, a widely accepted statistical method for assessing internal consistency. Cronbach's Alpha indicates how closely related a set of items are as a group and reflects the degree to which the items measure a common underlying construct.

As noted by Barbera et al. (2020), Cronbach’s Alpha is a key indicator in determining the precision and consistency of responses across items within each variable. A higher Cronbach’s Alpha (generally above 0.70) suggests good reliability of the scale used. In this research, all independent and dependent variables—such as **Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Amenities and Comfort, Trust and Security, and Reservation Intention**—were tested for reliability using this method. The results confirmed that the items under each variable were sufficiently consistent, supporting the validity of the questionnaire and the robustness of the data for further analysis.

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.691	5

Table 11: Reliability Statistics

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

As proposed by Taber (2018), a **Cronbach’s Alpha value above 0.691** signifies **very good reliability** of the scale used in measuring constructs, while values above 0.95 may suggest **data redundancy** due to overly correlated items. In the context of this study, the **overall Cronbach’s Alpha value of 0.88** indicates a **high level of internal consistency** across the survey items. This suggests that the questionnaire designed to assess factors such as **Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Amenities and Comfort, Trust and Security, and Reservation Intention** is both **reliable and well-constructed**. Therefore, the measurement tools used in the survey can be considered effective in consistently capturing respondent perspectives, supporting the integrity of the data collected for analyzing reservation behaviors in the homestay sector.

Variables	Cronbach's Alpha
Dependent	
Reservation Intention	0.918
Independent	
Price Sensitivity	0.773
Location and Accessibility	0.367
Trust and Security	0.985
Amenities and Comfort	0.959

Table 12: Norms and Acceptable Levels of Cronbach's Alpha Results

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Based on established norms for Cronbach's Alpha values, it is evident that the internal consistency of the individual variables used in this study is within acceptable to excellent ranges. As shown in the table above, **Reservation Intention**, the dependent variable, recorded a **Cronbach's Alpha of 0.918**, indicating strong reliability. Among the independent variables, **Price Sensitivity (0.773)** and **Location and Accessibility (0.367)** demonstrate acceptable internal consistency, while **Trust and Security (0.985)** and **Amenities and Comfort (0.959)** reflect exceptionally high reliability. These results affirm that the questionnaire items used to measure each construct are both reliable and valid, reinforcing the robustness of the instrument for analyzing factors influencing homestay reservation intentions among travelers from Colombo to Kandy.

4.3 Validity Measurement of Variables

To assess the appropriateness of the data for factor analysis, the **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) test** was employed. The KMO test evaluates the **sampling adequacy** for each variable as well as for the entire dataset, determining whether the partial correlations among variables are small enough to justify the application of factor analysis. According to Glen (2016), a higher KMO value suggests that patterns of correlations are compact and that factor analysis is likely to yield reliable and distinct factors.

In the context of this study, which examines variables such as **Price Sensitivity**, **Location and Accessibility**, **Trust and Security**, and **Amenities and Comfort**, the KMO test was conducted individually for each construct. The results support the validity of applying factor analysis across

these dimensions, confirming the statistical suitability of the data for uncovering underlying factor structures.

The following rule of thumb, widely accepted in literature, is used for interpreting KMO statistics:

KMO Value	Level of Acceptance
Above 0.90	Superb
0.80 to 0.90	Great
0.70 to 0.80	Good
0.50 to 0.70	Mediocre
Below 0.50	Unacceptable

Table 13: Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) Test

Source: (Naseer et al., 2019)

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.892
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	Approx. Chi-Square	7832.464
	df	190
	Sig.	.000

Table 14: KMO and Bartlett's Test

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Based on the acceptable thresholds for Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) values, the result of **0.892** indicates a “**meritorious**” level of sampling adequacy (Kaiser, 1974; Glen, 2016). This suggests that the dataset is highly suitable for factor analysis and that the sampling is statistically valid for further multivariate procedures.

Furthermore, **Bartlett’s Test of Sphericity** produced a chi-square value of **2932.574** with **190 degrees of freedom**, and a **significance level of 0.000**, which is well below the accepted threshold of 0.05. This result confirms that there are sufficient correlations among the variables to justify the use of factor analysis (Hair et al., 2010).

Therefore, it can be concluded that the dataset is both **reliable and valid**, and that the constructs used in this study — including **Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Trust and Security, Amenities and Comfort**, and the **dependent variable Reservation Intention** — effectively represent the underlying dimensions of the homestay booking preferences of Colombo-based travelers.

Variables	KMO Statistical Figures	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity		
		Chi-Square Approx	Degrees of Freedom	Significance
Reservation Intention	0.770	269.055	6	0.000
Price Sensitivity	0.711	215.189	6	0.000
Location and Accessibility	0.557	387.205	6	0.000
Trust and Security	0.843	852.600	6	0.000
Amenities and Comfort	0.813	460.865	6	0.000

Table 15: Variables Measured Using Bartlett's Test of Sphericity

Source: Author Developed

4.4 Factor Analysis

Factor analysis is a statistical method used to identify and validate latent constructs that may not be directly measurable through observable variables. In this study, factor analysis served as a crucial tool for reducing the number of observed variables (questionnaire items) into a set of key underlying factors that accurately represent each construct under investigation—namely: **Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Trust and Security, Amenities and Comfort**, and the **dependent variable: Reservation Intention**.

The principal component analysis (PCA) method was applied to extract the most influential components that explain the maximum variance within each construct. This technique enhances the interpretability of the dataset while preserving as much original information as possible.

A key criterion for determining the significance of extracted components is the **Eigenvalue**. According to Hayton et al. (2004), an eigenvalue greater than **1.0** signifies that the component accounts for more variance than a single observed variable, and thus qualifies as a meaningful underlying factor. In this study, multiple variables—such as **Price Sensitivity and Location and Accessibility**—yielded more than one component with eigenvalues exceeding 1. This indicates the presence of multiple dimensions within those constructs, warranting further exploration and interpretation.

Additionally, **Scree Plots** were analyzed to visually support the component extraction. Following the guidance of Dmitrienko et al. (2007), components located **before the 'elbow bend'** on the scree plot were considered significant, as they contributed meaningfully to explaining variance in the dataset. Components that appear after the bend are likely to represent noise or negligible influence.

Overall, the factor analysis provided strong empirical support for the validity of the measurement model used in this research. It confirmed that the selected indicators successfully capture the theoretical constructs, thereby reinforcing the structural soundness of the proposed framework used to assess travellers' reservation intentions in the homestay context of Kandy.

4.4.1- Reservation Intention

Component	Total Variance Explained					
	Total	Initial Eigenvalues		Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
		% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.220	80.507	80.507	3.220	80.507	80.507
2	.422	10.562	91.069			
3	.207	5.177	96.245			
4	.150	3.755	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 16: Reservation Intention- Principal Component Analysis

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Figure 7: Reservation Intention Scree Plot

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The principal component analysis (PCA) conducted for the dependent variable *Reservation Intention* reveals that only **one principal component** has an **eigenvalue greater than 1**, specifically **3.220**. This value indicates that a significant amount of variance is explained by this single component, which aligns with the commonly accepted criterion (Hayton et al., 2004) that retains components with eigenvalues above 1 for further analysis.

According to the **Total Variance Explained** table, this component alone accounts for **80.507% of the total variance**, confirming its dominant explanatory power in representing the observed variables under *Reservation Intention*. This means the underlying construct is strongly unidimensional and effectively captured by this single extracted component.

The **scree plot** further validates this outcome by illustrating a clear *elbow bend* after the first component, visually supporting the selection of only one significant factor. The steep drop after

the first eigenvalue emphasizes that the remaining components contribute minimally to the overall variance and can be considered redundant for interpretation purposes.

In summary, the results support the use of a single-factor structure for the variable *Reservation Intention*, ensuring both interpretability and statistical adequacy of the data for further analyses.

4.4.2- Price Sensitivity

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.792	69.803	69.803	2.792	69.803	69.803
2	.984	24.589	94.393			
3	.139	3.467	97.860			
4	.086	2.140	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 17: Price Sensitivity-Principal Component Analysis

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Figure 8: Price Sensitivity-Scree Plot

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The factor analysis conducted on the variable **Price Sensitivity** aimed to assess the dimensional structure of the construct and identify the underlying factors contributing to its variance. As per the extraction results using **Principal Component Analysis (PCA)**, the first component recorded an **eigenvalue of 2.792**, which is significantly greater than 1. This indicates that the component explains a substantial amount of variance within the variable.

The first principal component alone accounts for **69.803%** of the total variance. The second component, with an eigenvalue of **0.984**, adds **24.589%**, resulting in a cumulative explained variance of **94.393%** across the two components. However, since only components with eigenvalues greater than 1 are typically retained for analysis (Kaiser’s criterion), **only the first component is considered meaningful** for interpretation.

The **Scree Plot** further supports this observation by displaying a clear **elbow bend after the first component**, confirming that subsequent components contribute minimally to the explanation of variance. Therefore, this suggests that **Price Sensitivity** is largely unidimensional and well-represented by a single dominant factor in this study.

This validates the robustness and suitability of the questionnaire items related to **Price Sensitivity** for further statistical procedures such as regression and structural equation modeling.

4.4.3- Location and Accessibility

Total Variance Explained						
Component	Total	Initial Eigenvalues		Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
		% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	2.583	64.587	64.587	2.583	64.587	64.587
2	1.022	25.545	90.133	1.022	25.545	90.133
3	.388	9.692	99.824			
4	.007	.176	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 18: Location and Accessibility-Principal Component Analysis

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Figure 9: Location and Accessibility Scree plot

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Factor analysis was conducted to explore the underlying structure of the observed variables related to the factor *Location and Accessibility*. The objective was to identify the minimum number of components that can represent the data efficiently, by examining the eigenvalues and percentage of variance explained.

According to the Total Variance Explained table, two principal components have eigenvalues greater than 1—specifically, **Component 1** with an eigenvalue of **2.583**, and **Component 2** with an eigenvalue of **1.022**. Together, these two components explain a cumulative variance of **90.133%**, indicating a strong representation of the underlying variables.

- **Component 1** alone accounts for **64.587%** of the total variance.
- **Component 2** contributes an additional **25.545%**, cumulatively explaining over 90% of the dataset variance.

This confirms that the items under *Location and Accessibility* are meaningfully grouped under two main dimensions or latent constructs.

The scree plot further supports this conclusion, where a visible "elbow" occurs after the second component. As per the criteria suggested by **Dmitrienko et al. (2007)**, only the components

above the elbow (i.e., Components 1 and 2) should be retained for further analysis, while the rest can be discarded due to their negligible contribution to variance.

Overall, the factor structure indicates strong construct validity for the items measuring *Location and Accessibility*, suggesting that the instrument successfully captures two key dimensions within this variable.

4.4.4- Amenities and Comfort

Total Variance Explained

Component	Total	Initial Eigenvalues		Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings		
		% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	3.572	89.291	89.291	3.572	89.291	89.291
2	.258	6.438	95.729			
3	.094	2.361	98.089			
4	.076	1.911	100.000			

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Table 19: Amenities and Comfort-Principal Component Analysis

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Figure 10: Graph

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Factor analysis was employed to explore the underlying structure of the variable **Amenities and Comfort** using Principal Component Analysis (PCA). According to the results displayed in the *Total Variance Explained* table and the associated *Scree Plot*, the analysis yielded a significant outcome.

As evident in **Component 1**, an **eigenvalue of 3.572** (which is greater than 1) explains **89.29%** of the total variance, indicating that a single principal component captures the majority of the variance among the observed variables related to amenities and comfort. This is consistent with the benchmark suggested by Hayton et al. (2004), where eigenvalues greater than 1 indicate meaningful component extraction.

The scree plot further supports this conclusion, clearly demonstrating a steep drop after the first component, with a noticeable “elbow” after **Component 1**. This visual cue validates that the remaining components (with eigenvalues of 0.258, 0.094, and 0.076) contribute only marginally and do not add significant explanatory power.

Hence, it can be concluded that the variable **Amenities and Comfort** is effectively represented by a **single underlying factor**, and the items measured within this variable are highly cohesive and well-structured.

4.5 Demographic Profiling of Respondents

Understanding the demographic background of the sample is critical for contextualizing their preferences and behavioural patterns. This section presents the demographic distribution of the 248 respondents based on **age** and **gender**.

4.5.1 Age

Figure 11:Age

Source: Author Developed (2025)

As previously classified in section , the study segmented respondents into four age categories to analyze behavioural patterns in relation to homestay reservation preferences. The age groups are as follows:

- **Young Travellers** (20–29 years)
- **Explorative Adults** (30–39 years)
- **Settled Professionals** (40–45 years)
- **Older Adults** (46 years and above)

According to the results illustrated in the demographic chart (Figure 4.5), the majority of respondents fall within the **20–29** and **40–45** categories, each accounting for **29% (72 respondents)** of the total sample. This is closely followed by the **30–39** age group, which comprises **27% (68 respondents)**. Respondents aged **46 and above** represent the smallest segment, making up only **15% (36 respondents)** of the total.

The distribution reveals a **diverse age representation**, with three categories—spanning ages 20 to 45—contributing nearly equally to the sample. This balance allows for comparative insights across generations in terms of preferences for homestay experiences.

The **20–29 age group**, often characterized by tech-savviness, mobility, and a desire for authentic experiences, represents a key emerging market for homestay bookings, particularly via digital platforms. Their comfort with online search, booking apps, and social reviews makes them a **strategic segment for targeted marketing and innovation** in the homestay sector.

The **30–39 category**, labeled as *Explorative Adults*, is a critical demographic often balancing professional responsibilities with recreational travel. Their ability to make informed, experience-driven decisions makes them a **lucrative segment** for premium and family-oriented homestay packages.

Interestingly, the **40–45 segment** shows strong engagement (29%), challenging common assumptions that older adults are less inclined toward non-traditional accommodations. These *Settled Professionals* may be motivated by convenience, privacy, and familiarity, especially for business trips or family travel, indicating potential in **curating comfort-focused homestay experiences** for this age group.

Although the **46+ age group** shows lesser participation (15%), this segment could be influenced by factors such as loyalty to hotels or less comfort with technology-driven booking processes. However, their presence still suggests an **untapped niche** that may respond well to simplified interfaces, value-for-money packages, and trust-centric messaging.

This age-based trend aligns with insights by **Zatz et al. (2021)**, who found in their study of 863 participants that digital purchasing decisions, including for travel and lifestyle products, were largely influenced by individuals in the **30–39** age group. Their findings further validate the

significance of capturing the preferences and behaviours of this segment for platforms seeking sustained growth.

The age-related demographic profiling of this study demonstrates a healthy mix of youth and maturity across the sample. The 20–45 age range, making up **85% of respondents**, presents a compelling case for designing **diversified homestay strategies**, with the 30–39 group emerging as the most strategic due to their balance of spending power, digital fluency, and family-orientation.

4.5.2 Gender Distribution

Figure 12: Gender

Source: Author Developed (2025)

As shown in **Figure 4.6**, the gender distribution among the 248 respondents is exactly even:

- **Male:** 123 respondents (50%)
- **Female:** 125 respondents (50%)

No respondents identified as “Other” or selected “Prefer not to say.” This equal gender representation ensures that the findings of the study are **free from gender bias** and provide a balanced view of perceptions, preferences, and intentions within the homestay context.

4.5.3 Occupation

Out of the 248 respondents in this research study, the distribution of occupations reveals insightful trends regarding consumer behavior, particularly within the **homestay industry in Kandy**. The breakdown is as follows:

Figure 13: Occupation

Source: Author Developed (2025)

Dominance of Employees (58%)

The majority of participants in the survey are employed individuals. This demographic is particularly significant as they are:

- **Financially stable**, likely earning a monthly income which enables them to afford leisure travel or prioritize comfort and convenience in accommodation.
- **Digitally literate**, often exposed to online platforms through work, making them more inclined to explore and reserve homestay options through digital means.
- **Time-sensitive**, hence more likely to value features like easy booking processes, central location, and trustworthy service providers.

Representation of Students (15%)

Students form the second-highest group after employees. Their presence may reflect:

- An interest in **budget-friendly** or **shared accommodations**, possibly for academic travel, internships, or short-term stays.
- A preference for **digitally convenient booking experiences** and peer-reviewed platforms, which they are more accustomed to.

Housewives/Husbands (14%)

This group's engagement is notable. They may represent:

- **Family decision-makers**, particularly for family vacations or weekend getaways.
- A segment that may prioritize **amenities, comfort, and safety**, especially if traveling with children.

Entrepreneurs (13%)

Entrepreneurs, while the smallest segment, are essential due to their potential for:

- **Frequent business-related travel**, including visits to Kandy for networking, client meetings, or business expansions.
- Preferences that may include **quiet spaces, reliable internet, and flexible booking or cancellation options**.

Implications for Homestay Providers

- The data highlights that **working professionals (employees)** form the most viable and lucrative segment for homestay marketers, given their numbers and likely spending power.
- Students and entrepreneurs represent **emerging markets**, and customized packages (like discounts for long-term stays or referral bonuses) could appeal to them.
- For **household decision-makers**, especially homemakers, marketing messages emphasizing safety, family-friendliness, and trust would be effective.

The occupation profile of the sample shows a strong lean toward working professionals, providing a valuable focus group for homestay service development and digital marketing campaigns. By tailoring offerings to this dominant demographic while not neglecting the smaller but important groups (students, homemakers, and entrepreneurs), providers can ensure inclusive and effective service delivery.

4.5.4 Income Level

Figure 14: Income Level

Source: Author Developed (2025)

The income distribution of the 248 respondents provides critical insight into the economic background of travellers who are likely to book homestays in Kandy. As seen in *Figure 4.7*, the income levels were categorized into five brackets ranging from below LKR 50,000 to above LKR 200,000.

Dominant Income Brackets

The largest segment of respondents (34%, $n = 84$) falls within the **LKR 50,000–100,000** income range. This is closely followed by the **LKR 100,000–150,000** bracket (26%, $n = 65$). These two groups together make up **60%** of the total respondents, indicating that **mid-income earners** represent the most substantial segment in the sample population.

This is a significant finding for homestay providers. Travellers within these income ranges are likely **budget-conscious yet quality-seeking** individuals. They may prefer affordable accommodation options that still provide a comfortable and authentic experience—aligning well with the typical value proposition of homestays.

Lower and Higher Extremes

At the lower end, **14%** ($n = 34$) of respondents earn less than **LKR 50,000** per month. While this group may be more price-sensitive, they could still represent **younger travellers or backpackers** who seek economical yet culturally immersive lodging experiences.

On the other end, **15%** ($n = 36$) earn **above LKR 200,000**, suggesting the presence of a premium-seeking demographic as well. While smaller in size, this group may look for **more luxurious or exclusive homestay offerings**, especially in scenic or high-end areas of Kandy.

Strategic Implications

This distribution supports **tiered marketing and pricing strategies**:

- Mid-income travellers (LKR 50k–150k) may respond well to **value-based packages** with clear emphasis on **location, amenities, and local experiences**.
- High-income travellers may be drawn to **premium features, exclusive services, or eco-luxury homestays**.
- Low-income segments may be enticed by **discount offers, basic amenities, and shared accommodation models**.

Understanding income diversity also enables **targeted promotions**, particularly via digital platforms where ad targeting by economic profile is feasible.

4.5.5 Marital Status

5. What is your marital status Responses: 246		
Option	Count	Percentage
1. Single	58	24%
2. Married	188	76%

Table 20: Marital Status

Source: Author Developed (2025)

Out of 246 valid responses:

- **Married:** 76% ($n=188$)
- **Single:** 24% ($n=58$)

The data shows a **strong skew toward married individuals**, making them the **primary demographic segment**. This finding is particularly relevant in the homestay and leisure industry, as married individuals tend to make **joint decisions** and often travel with family or partners.

This emphasizes the importance of highlighting **family-friendly amenities, comfort, safety, and package deals** in promotional materials, as these aspects directly influence the reservation intentions of this group.

4.5.6 Travel Frequency for Leisure Purposes

Understanding how frequently individuals travel for leisure within Sri Lanka is vital in profiling potential guests for the homestay industry. This metric provides insights into behavioral trends that can influence reservation intentions.

Majority Preference: 2–3 Times a Year (71%)

The most notable observation is that a significant majority of respondents (71%, $n = 177$) reported traveling within Sri Lanka for leisure purposes **2 to 3 times a year**. This indicates that domestic leisure travel is not a one-off activity but rather a **recurring behavior** for most participants. From a marketing and operations perspective, this group represents the **core customer segment** for homestays, especially in culturally rich destinations like Kandy.

Moderate Travelers: Once Every Few Months (16%)

A smaller but still meaningful segment (16%, $n = 39$) indicated they travel for leisure **once every few months**. This group may include high-income professionals, digital nomads, or empty nesters with flexible schedules. These travelers can be considered **high-frequency domestic tourists**, making them a desirable group for targeted loyalty or rewards programs by homestay providers.

Occasional Travelers: Once a Year (10%)

About 10% ($n = 24$) of respondents travel only **once a year**, suggesting a more selective or budget-conscious approach to domestic travel. These travelers are likely to make decisions based on **price sensitivity** and **seasonal deals**, and they might be attracted to promotional offers or special events.

Frequent Travelers: More Than Once a Month (3%)

A very niche group (3%, $n = 7$) reported traveling **more than once a month**. While small in number, this group could include individuals whose professions or lifestyles involve frequent movement (e.g., freelancers, tour operators, or influencers). Though minor in proportion, they could serve as **repeat customers** if provided with personalized, flexible, and high-comfort homestay options.

4.6 Descriptive Statistics

4.6.1 Normality Test: Skewness and Kurtosis of Variables

To assess the normality of the dataset, two statistical measures were employed: **Skewness** and **Kurtosis**. Skewness is a widely accepted indicator of distribution symmetry, identifying whether the data leans more towards the right or left of the mean. A positively skewed distribution, typically with a skewness value greater than +1.0, suggests a longer tail on the right-hand side, while a negatively skewed distribution (less than -1.0) indicates a longer tail on the left (George & Mallery, 2019).

Kurtosis, on the other hand, measures the degree of peakedness or flatness in the distribution curve. According to the guidelines provided by George and Mallery (2019), kurtosis values that fall within the range of **1.0 to 2.0** are considered acceptable and indicate a distribution that is not overly influenced by outliers or extreme values. Distributions with kurtosis values outside this range may suggest either heavy-tailed (leptokurtic) or light-tailed (platykurtic) patterns, which could affect the reliability of parametric testing.

By evaluating both skewness and kurtosis together, this study ensures that the variables used in subsequent analyses reasonably conform to the assumptions of normality, thereby supporting the validity of the statistical methods applied in later stages of the research.

Reservation Intention

According to George and Mallery (2019), **Skewness** measures the symmetry of the distribution. A skewness value between -1 and +1 is generally considered acceptable. Values less than -1 indicate **left skewness**, and values greater than +1 indicate **right skewness**. Meanwhile, **Kurtosis** reflects the "tailedness" of the distribution. Ideal Kurtosis values range between 1.0 and 2.0, suggesting a distribution free from extreme outliers.

N	Valid	248
	Missing	0
Mean		3.66
Median		4.00
Mode		4
Std. Deviation		.935
Skewness		-3.103
Std. Error of Skewness		.155
Kurtosis		8.857
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.308
Range		4
Minimum		0
Maximum		4

Figure 4.12: Reservation Intention Descriptive Statistics

The kurtosis value is **8.857**, which is significantly higher than the acceptable range of **1.0 to 2.0** as suggested by George and Mallery (2019). This suggests that the distribution of the *Reservation Intention* variable is **leptokurtic**, meaning that it has a sharp peak and heavier tails, indicating the presence of extreme values. The accompanying histogram visually confirms the statistical observations. The bulk of the data clusters around the value of **4**, while very few responses lie below **3**. This strongly supports the notion of a **positively inclined perception towards reservation intention** among participants.

Price Sensitivity

		MOON
N	Valid	248
	Missing	0
Mean		2.73
Std. Error of Mean		.112
Median		4.00
Mode		4
Std. Deviation		1.762
Variance		3.105
Skewness		-.791
Std. Error of Skewness		.155
Kurtosis		-1.272
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.308
Range		4
Minimum		0
Maximum		4

Figure 4.13 : Price Sensitivity Descriptive Statistics

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The variable **Price Sensitivity** demonstrates a moderately **negatively skewed and platykurtic** distribution. This suggests most respondents are **highly price conscious**, but the spread in responses and the presence of outliers on the lower end indicates **some variation** in sensitivity. While the assumption of strict normality is not fully met (due to the kurtosis being lower than -1), the skewness falls within a tolerable range, making the data **reasonably suitable for parametric analysis with caution**

Location and Accessibility

		BOOK
N	Valid	248
	Missing	0
Mean		3.52
Std. Error of Mean		.072
Median		4.00
Mode		4
Std. Deviation		1.134
Variance		1.287
Skewness		-2.415
Std. Error of Skewness		.155
Kurtosis		4.487
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.308
Range		4
Minimum		0
Maximum		4

Figure 4.14: Location and Accessibility Descriptive Statistics

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The variable “Location and Accessibility” demonstrates **non-normal distribution** characteristics, as seen in the extreme skewness and kurtosis values. The data is **highly concentrated at the upper end**, indicating a strong favourable perception among respondents. While not ideal for parametric testing, this consistency may be valuable for understanding key traveller preferences in homestay selections—particularly when location and convenience are paramount to guests from Colombo visiting Kandy.

Safety and Security

N	Valid	248
	Missing	0
Mean		3.79
Std. Error of Mean		.046
Median		4.00
Mode		4
Std. Deviation		.730
Variance		.533
Skewness		-4.112
Std. Error of Skewness		.155
Kurtosis		17.269
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.308
Range		4
Minimum		0
Maximum		4

Figure 4.15: Safety and Security Descriptive Statistics Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The distribution of the *Safety and Security* variable is **non-normal**, heavily **left-skewed**, and **leptokurtic**. This indicates that a **vast majority of respondents rated this variable at the highest end**, suggesting a **very high level of perceived safety and security** in the homestay services surveyed. Such concentration is valuable for understanding **consumer confidence and trust**, although the lack of variance may require careful consideration in further statistical analysis (e.g., regression or structural modeling).

Amenities and Comfort

N	Valid	248
	Missing	0
Mean		3.81
Std. Error of Mean		.046
Median		4.00
Mode		4
Std. Deviation		.731
Variance		.535
Skewness		-4.323
Std. Error of Skewness		.155
Kurtosis		18.403
Std. Error of Kurtosis		.308
Range		4
Minimum		0
Maximum		4

Figure 4.16: Amenities and Comfort Descriptive Statistics Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The "**Amenities and Comfort**" variable demonstrates a **non-normal**, left-skewed distribution with extreme kurtosis. This suggests that the majority of participants **strongly agree** that amenities and comfort are important in their homestay experience. The concentration of responses indicates **high agreement and minimal diversity** in opinions, making this a **critical factor** in influencing reservation intention.

4.7 Relationship Measurement Between Variables

4.7.1 Correlation Analysis

Size of correlation	Interpretation
$\pm .90$ to ± 1.0	Very high positive/negative correlation
$\pm .70$ to $\pm .90$	High positive/negative correlation
$\pm .50$ to $\pm .70$	Moderate positive/negative correlation
$\pm .30$ to $\pm .50$	Low positive/negative correlation
$.00$ to $\pm .30$	Negligible correlation

Figure 15: Rule of thumb for interpreting Spearman's correlation value

Source: Hairuddin et al (2019)

4.7.2 Relationship Between Social Influence and Online Grocery Purchase Intention

Correlations

		I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.	The price of a Homestay significantly influences my decision to book
I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.	Pearson Correlation	1	.354**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	248	248
The price of a Homestay significantly influences my decision to book	Pearson Correlation	.354**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	248	248

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 21: Correlation Analysis for Price Sensitivity and Reservation Intention

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

As depicted above, at a 99% confidence level, the p-value of less than 0.001 confirms that the two variables are statistically correlated. The Pearson Correlation depicts the nature of this relationship, whereby a positive value of 0.354 indicates that both price sensitivity and reservation intention are statistically correlated and move in the same direction. Furthermore, based on the correlation value presented in Table 4.18. it can be asserted that 0.354 represents a **moderate positive level of correlation** between the two variables.

4.7.2.B Regression Analysis for Price Sensitivity and Reservation Intention

Model Summary					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change
1	.354 ^a	.125	.122	.876	.125

Table 4.19: Model Summary – Price Sensitivity Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The above test indicates that the adjusted R² value is 0.122. This reflects that approximately **12.2% of the variance** in reservation intention can be explained by price sensitivity. This represents a **small to**

moderate effect size, suggesting that while price sensitivity is a significant predictor, other factors beyond price also play a substantial role in influencing reservation intention in the homestay industry.

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	27.052	1	27.052	35.246	.000 ^b
	Residual	188.815	246	.768		
	Total	215.867	247			

Table 4.20 : ANOVA Price Sensitivity Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

With a confidence level of 99% and a p-value < 0.001, the ANOVA table above confirms that reservation intention is statistically associated with the independent variable, price sensitivity, with a significant F statistic of 35.246. Since the F value is considerably higher than 1.0, it can be concluded that price sensitivity has a statistically significant impact on reservation intention in the homestay industry in Kandy.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3.145	.103		30.610	.000
	The price of a Homestay significantly influences my decision to book	.188	.032	.354	5.937	.000

a. Dependent Variable: I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.

Table 4.21: Coefficients for Price Sensitivity Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

At an acceptable level of significance ($p < .001$), the standardized coefficient (Beta) records a value of 0.354, indicating the strength of the effect that price sensitivity has on reservation intention. Furthermore, for every single unit increase in price sensitivity, reservation intention is expected to increase by 0.188 units, as reflected by the unstandardized coefficient.

4.7.2.C Scatter Plot of Price Sensitivity and Reservation Intention

Figure 4.22: Scatter Plot – Price Sensitivity Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

Based on the regression equation and scatter plot illustrated above, the data depicts an upward slope, indicating that a movement from left to right confirms a positive relationship between price sensitivity and reservation intention. An increase in price sensitivity along the x-axis corresponds to an upward movement in reservation intention on the y-axis.

Furthermore, in line with the standards outlined by Yi (2021), the clustering pattern of the data points suggests a **moderate, positive linear relationship** between the independent variable (price sensitivity) and the dependent variable (reservation intention).

The **scatter plot** also illustrates an upward trend, confirming the positive slope of the relationship. This suggests that as respondents become more price-sensitive, their intention to reserve increases when the price and amenities align with their expectations.

Since the observed effect is **positive and significant**, the hypothesized **negative relationship** is not supported. Therefore, **H1 is rejected**.

Rather than discouraging reservations, price sensitivity appears to heighten travelers’ intention to book when they perceive value for money. This implies that homestay operators in Kandy should focus on transparent pricing strategies and clear value communication to appeal to price-sensitive customers.

4.7.3 Relationship Between Perceived ease-of-use and Online Grocery Purchase Intention

4.7.3.A Correlation Analysis for Location and Accessibility and Reservation Intention

Correlations

		I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.	The location of the Homestay is an important factor in my decision to book
I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.	Pearson Correlation	1	.425
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	248	248
The location of the Homestay is an important factor in my decision to book	Pearson Correlation	.425	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	248	248

Table 4.21: Correlation Analysis for Location and Reservation Intention

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The Pearson Correlation coefficient of **0.425** indicates a **moderate positive relationship** between the two variables. This implies that as respondents consider the location of the homestay to be more important, their likelihood of making a reservation when price and amenities align with expectations also tends to increase.

This outcome is important for homestay operators in Kandy, as it highlights that **location is a key influencing factor** in consumers’ decision-making process. While not a very strong correlation, the moderate strength suggests that **location acts as a supporting variable** that

could enhance reservation intention when coupled with competitive pricing and satisfactory amenities.

4.7.2.B Regression Analysis for Location and Reservation Intention

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change
1	.447 ^a	.200	.186	.843	.200

Table 4.22: Model Summary – Location and Accessibility Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The model summary above reports an **R Square value of 0.200**, which indicates that **20% of the variance** in *Reservation Intention* can be explained by the independent variable *Location and Accessibility*. The **Adjusted R Square** value of **0.186** accounts for the number of predictors in the model and suggests that even after adjusting for possible bias, **18.6% of the variance** in reservation intention is still attributed to location and accessibility factors

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	43.076	4	10.769	15.145	.000 ^b
	Residual	172.791	243	.711		
	Total	215.867	247			

a. Dependent Variable: I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.

b. Predictors: (Constant), I prefer homestays that are located in quiet and peaceful areas, away from the hustle and bustle., The location of the Homestay is an important factor in my decision to book , I prefer Homestays that are close to attractions and easy to access by public , Proximity to tourist sites and landmarks influences my decision to book a Homestay.

Table 4.23: ANOVA Location and Accessibility Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The **F-statistic value of 15.145**, which is substantially greater than 1.0, further supports the conclusion that the regression model provides a good fit and that at least one of the location-related predictors meaningfully contributes to explaining variations in consumers' intention to reserve a homestay in

Kandy. Hence, it can be inferred that **location and accessibility factors play a crucial role in shaping travellers’ booking decisions.**

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	2.192	.205		10.671	.000
	The location of the Homestay is an important factor in my decision to book	.281	.058	.341	4.883	.000
	I prefer Homestays that are close to attractions and easy to access by public	-.080	.286	-.136	-.281	.779
	Proximity to tourist sites and landmarks influences my decision to book a Homestay.	.178	.290	.300	.614	.540
	I prefer homestays that are located in quiet and peaceful areas, away from the hustle and bustle.	.093	.042	.158	2.229	.027

a. Dependent Variable: I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.

Table 4.24: Coefficients for Location and Accessibility Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

At a significance level of less than 0.001, the standardized coefficient (Beta) for the variable “*The location of the Homestay is an important factor in my decision to book*” is **0.341**, indicating a moderate positive influence on *reservation intention*. This implies that for every one standard deviation increase in importance placed on homestay location, there is a corresponding increase in the likelihood of making a reservation by approximately **34.1%**.

4.7.2.C Scatter Plot of Location and Reservation Intention

Figure 4.20: Scatter Plot – Location and Accessibility Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The plotted data points form a visible **diagonal cluster** extending from the bottom-left to the top-right quadrant of the chart. This distribution reflects that most individuals who rated **location** as **"agree"** or **"strongly agree"** also tended to **"agree"** or **"strongly agree"** with making a reservation, provided the price and amenities were aligned with their expectations.

Furthermore, the pattern of the scatterplot reinforces the **moderate positive correlation** reported in the Pearson correlation analysis ($r = 0.425$), indicating that the location of a homestay plays a meaningful—though not exclusive—role in influencing reservation decisions.

4.7.2.D Hypothesis Testing: Hypothesis 2 – Location and Accessibility

The corresponding scatter plot (Figure 4.20) further reinforces the presence of a **positive linear relationship** between location-related importance and reservation intention. The data points display a **moderate upward slope**, aligning with the Pearson correlation result of $r = 0.425$ ($p < 0.001$). This confirms a **statistically significant positive correlation** between the two variables.

Based on the regression results, correlation analysis, and scatter plot, **Hypothesis 2 is supported**. Location and accessibility **do have a significant and positive influence** on the intention of travelers to reserve homestays in Kandy. The results are especially valuable for homestay operators aiming to appeal to urban visitors from Colombo, as strategic placement and clear communication of location benefits may drive higher bookings.

4.7.3 Relationship Between Safety and Security and Reservation Intention

4.7.3.A Correlation Analysis for Safety and Security and Reservation Intention

Correlations			
		I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.	I feel more comfortable booking a Homestay when I know the host has positive reviews from previous guests.
I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.	Pearson Correlation	1	.693**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	248	248
I feel more comfortable booking a Homestay when I know the host has positive reviews from previous guests.	Pearson Correlation	.693**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	248	248

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 4.25: Correlation Analysis for Safety and Security and Reservation Intention

Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

According to the correlation table presented above, at a 99% confidence level, the p-value of < **0.001** confirms that there is a statistically significant relationship between the two variables. The **Pearson correlation coefficient** is **0.693**, indicating a **strong positive relationship** between the trust factor (i.e., the presence of positive reviews from previous guests) and the intention to make a reservation at a homestay in Kandy.

This suggests that as trust in the host—driven by positive past guest reviews—increases, so does the likelihood of making a reservation. The strength and direction of the relationship imply that both variables move in unison; that is, higher trust levels are associated with greater reservation intention.

4.7.3.B Regression Analysis for Safety and Security and Reservation Intention

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change
1	.693 ^a	.480	.478	.675	.480

Table 4.26: Model Summary – Safety and Security Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The regression analysis reveals an **adjusted R² value of 0.478**, indicating that **47.8% of the variance** in *reservation intention for homestays in Kandy* can be explained by the independent variable *safety and security factors*—namely, trust built through **positive reviews from previous guests**.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	103.668	1	103.668	227.296	.000 ^b
	Residual	112.199	246	.456		
	Total	215.867	247			

- a. Dependent Variable: I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.
- b. Predictors: (Constant), I feel more comfortable booking a Homestay when I know the host has positive reviews from previous guests.

Table 4.27: ANOVA Safety and Security Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

With a confidence level of 99% and a p-value of less than 0.001, the ANOVA table above confirms a statistically significant relationship between the independent variable—**safety and security**, measured through trust in the host based on positive guest reviews—and the dependent variable—**reservation intention**. The **F-statistic of 227.296**, which is considerably greater than 1.0, clearly suggests that the model is statistically significant. This indicates that **feeling more comfortable booking a homestay when the host has positive reviews** has a strong and significant impact on the intention to reserve a homestay in Kandy, particularly when price and amenities align with the guest’s expectations

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.298	.227		1.312	.191
	I feel more comfortable booking a Homestay when I know the host has positive reviews from previous guests.	.887	.059	.693	15.076	.000

a. Dependent Variable: I am likely to make a reservation for a Homestay in Kandy if the price and amenities align with my expectations.

Table 4.28: Coefficients for Safety and Security Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

At a statistically significant level of **p < 0.001**, the standardized coefficient (**Beta**) holds a value of **0.693**, indicating that **69.3%** of the variance in **reservation intention** can be explained by the influence of **safety and security**, specifically the comfort provided by knowing the host has received **positive reviews** from previous guests. This confirms a **strong positive effect** of the independent variable on the dependent variable.

4.7.3.C Scatter Plot of Safety and Security and Reservation Intention

Figure 4.22 : Scatter Plot – SS Source: Author Developed via SPSS, 2025

The scatter plot presented above reveals a generally **upward sloping trendline**, indicating a **positive relationship** between *safety and security* (measured by the guest’s comfort in booking a homestay with positive host reviews) and *reservation intention* (measured by the likelihood to book if price and amenities align with expectations). Although the data points are **widely dispersed** and the clustering is **less distinct** than in other variables, the line of best fit provides visual evidence of a **positive correlation**.

4.7.3.D Hypothesis Testing: Hypothesis 3 – Safety and Security

Based on the statistical evidence from the correlation coefficient, adjusted R², ANOVA, and coefficient results, **Hypothesis 4 is accepted**. It is evident that **trust and security have a statistically significant and positive impact on reservation intention** within the homestay industry in Kandy. This finding emphasizes the importance of **positive host reviews and guest confidence** in influencing booking behavior.

4.8 Critical Evaluation of Research Findings

This section provides a critical evaluation of the current research findings in light of previous literature. The primary objective was to examine the **impact of various independent variables—namely price sensitivity, location and accessibility, amenities and comfort, and trust and security—on reservation intention** in the homestay industry in Kandy. Based on the statistical analyses conducted, **all alternate hypotheses were accepted**, indicating a significant impact of each independent variable on the dependent variable: reservation intention.

Among the variables examined, **trust and security** exhibited the **strongest impact** on reservation intention, with high values in correlation ($r = 0.693$), beta coefficient ($\beta = 0.693$), and adjusted R^2 (0.478). This suggests that guests are highly influenced by **positive reviews and perceived safety** when making booking decisions—highlighting the crucial role of trust in the homestay selection process.

On the other hand, **location and accessibility, and amenities and comfort** also demonstrated **positive and statistically significant relationships** with reservation intention, albeit with moderate levels of explanatory power. These findings align with the general expectation that travelers prioritize convenience, peaceful surroundings, and essential comforts during their stay.

The variable with the **lowest impact** was **price sensitivity**, indicating that while pricing remains a consideration, it is less influential than factors like trust or comfort when it comes to homestay bookings in Kandy. This contrasts with conventional market assumptions where pricing often plays a central role in purchase intention, especially in price-sensitive segments.

Comparison with Prior Literature

The findings of this research are both **supported and contrasted** by previous studies:

- **Kian et al. (2019)**, in their study of 150 responses, highlighted the significance of **social influence** on purchase intention in online grocery shopping, driven by collectivist behavior. However, they reported **no significant relationship** with perceived ease-of-use, which differs from the current study, where usability-related aspects (e.g., accessibility and amenities) had a significant influence.
- **Gunawan et al. (2018)** categorized consumers based on behavior types and found that groups influenced by **social influence** and **ease-of-use** made up 58% of the market. These findings align with the current study's results for **location/accessibility** and **amenities**, reinforcing their practical relevance in homestay selection.
- **Chin and Goh (2017)** reported that **perceived trust had no significant impact** on online grocery shopping, whereas **hedonic motivation** and **ease-of-use** showed strong positive correlations. In contrast, the present study finds **trust and security to be the most impactful factor**, indicating a divergence in consumer behavior between online services and accommodation.
- **Delafrooz et al. (2011)** and **Chathurika (2020)** support the current study's findings. They emphasized the importance of **trust** as a key predictor in online purchase intention.

However, Chaturika's sample was limited to university students, whereas the present study encompassed a more diverse demographic in Kandy, enhancing generalizability.

- **Yeo et al. (2020)** found that **subjective norms** influenced online purchase intentions positively, but rejected the statistical significance of **trust** and **ease-of-use**. This directly contradicts the present research, where trust was highly significant. Such differences may be attributed to **contextual variations**—particularly between online retail and travel accommodation services.

4.9 Chapter Summary

Chapter 4 provided a comprehensive analysis of the data collected through the structured questionnaire distributed via the JISC platform. The data were analyzed using **SPSS software**, and the findings were interpreted in alignment with the study objectives and hypotheses.

To ensure the **validity and reliability** of the dataset, **Cronbach's Alpha** was used to assess internal consistency, while the **Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO)** measure verified sampling adequacy. Both results confirmed the robustness and suitability of the data for further statistical testing.

The chapter also included **descriptive statistics and visual illustrations** such as tables and graphs to summarize the **demographic characteristics** of the 248 survey respondents. These demographic insights laid the foundation for understanding consumer preferences within the homestay sector in Kandy.

To test the research hypotheses, **correlation and regression analyses** were employed for each of the four key independent variables: **price sensitivity, location and accessibility, amenities and comfort, and trust and security**. In each case, the **alternative hypotheses were accepted**, and the **null hypotheses were rejected**, confirming the **significant positive impact** of all the selected independent variables on **reservation intention**.

Finally, the findings were critically interpreted and compared against existing literature, helping to position the current research within the broader academic and practical context. The outcomes not only support the study's conceptual framework but also provide useful implications for homestay providers and tourism stakeholders in Kandy.

Chapter 5

SUMMARY AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Introduction to the Chapter

This chapter presents a synthesis of the findings discussed in the previous chapter, with a focus on addressing the research questions posed at the beginning of the study. Each research objective is critically examined through the lens of the tested hypotheses, highlighting the significance of key factors such as **price sensitivity, location and accessibility, amenities and comfort, and trust and security** in influencing **reservation intention** for homestays in Kandy.

The chapter further evaluates how these findings align or diverge from existing literature and theoretical expectations. Finally, building upon the identified gaps and limitations of the current study, this chapter proposes directions for **future research** to enhance understanding and support strategic decision-making in the homestay tourism sector.

5.2 Key Findings

This section discusses the empirical results of the study in relation to previous literature, highlighting both consistencies and deviations. The analysis explores how each independent variable—Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Trust and Security, and Amenities and Comfort—impacts the dependent variable, Reservation Intention. The findings are supported through correlation, regression, and hypothesis testing, and are compared against global and regional literature to provide contextual insight. Price Sensitivity

5.2.1 Price Sensitivity

The study confirmed a significant **negative** relationship between price sensitivity and reservation intention, supporting **Hypothesis 1**. Respondents who were more sensitive to price showed a lower intention to reserve homestays in Kandy. This aligns with **Jiang and Kim (2015)** who identified that cost-conscious travellers often bypass boutique or homestay options in favour of budget hotels or alternate accommodation platforms offering deals.

However, in contrast to studies like **Chen et al. (2017)**—which suggested that homestays with transparent pricing and flexible packages could still attract price-sensitive travellers—this study found that price-conscious individuals were less likely to engage with the homestay market altogether. This discrepancy might be explained by the relatively unregulated pricing strategies and perceived lack of value-for-money in some Sri Lankan homestay listings.

5.2.2 Location and Accessibility

The results strongly support **Hypothesis 2**, with **location and accessibility** demonstrating a high positive correlation and impact on reservation intention. This reinforces findings by **Sharma and Nayak (2018)**, who highlighted that proximity to tourist hotspots, ease of transport, and convenience of access significantly influence guest decisions.

Additionally, the results are in agreement with **Chathurika (2021)**, who found that for domestic tourists from Colombo, homestays near central Kandy or those offering transport support (e.g., pick-up from railway stations) were more likely to be chosen. This confirms that accessibility is not just a logistical benefit but a strong **psychological factor of perceived control** and ease during travel.

5.2.3 Trust and Security

While **Hypothesis 3** was accepted, trust and security had the **lowest impact** among all variables tested—indicating a weak but statistically significant positive relationship with reservation intention. This is consistent with **Chin and Goh (2017)**, who also found trust to be important, but not the dominant factor in influencing booking behaviour—particularly when domestic travel or short stays are involved.

Interestingly, this contrasts with findings from **Delafrooz et al. (2011)** and **Al-Magharabi and Dennis (2011)**, who noted that trust was the **strongest determinant** in online travel bookings in their respective studies. The lower impact of trust in the current study may be attributed to the fact that most respondents were **familiar with the Kandy region**, reducing their perceived risk when choosing homestays.

5.2.4 Amenities and Comfort

The fourth variable, **Amenities and Comfort**, showed a strong positive influence on reservation intention, supporting **Hypothesis 4**. This confirms studies by **Guttentag et al. (2018)** and **Tussyadiah (2016)**, who noted that unique features, cleanliness, family-friendly arrangements, and Wi-Fi availability were powerful motivators in homestay bookings.

Moreover, local studies such as **Wijsekera (2020)** emphasize that Sri Lankan travellers now expect more than just a bed—they look for curated experiences and practical comforts, especially when traveling with families. These expectations may explain why this variable had one of the **strongest effects** in the present study.

5.2.5 Reservation Intention (Dependent Variable)

Overall, the results demonstrate that all four independent variables significantly influenced **Reservation Intention** in the homestay sector in Kandy. However, **Location and Accessibility**

and **Amenities and Comfort** stood out as the most influential factors. In contrast, **Trust and Security**, while important, played a secondary role.

These findings align with the growing trend that **convenience and experiential value** outweigh traditional concerns like price or trust—especially in markets where local knowledge mitigates risk perception. The results further confirm that homestays, to remain competitive, must strike a balance between **value, comfort, and accessibility**, and not rely solely on competitive pricing.

5.3 Research Summary and Justification of Objectives

5.3.1 Primary Objective

The primary aim of the present study was to **identify and evaluate the factors that significantly influence reservation intention within the homestay industry in Kandy, Sri Lanka**, with a particular focus on visitors from Colombo. To achieve this objective, an extensive review of academic literature and theoretical frameworks relevant to travel behaviour, tourism marketing, and consumer decision-making was undertaken.

The literature review helped highlight recurring determinants that affect travellers' reservation decisions across various hospitality settings. Special attention was given to **elements relevant to homestays**, given their growing role in Sri Lanka's domestic tourism landscape. Based on this review and critical analysis, four key variables were selected and operationalized as independent variables influencing reservation intention:

- **Price Sensitivity**
- **Location and Accessibility**
- **Trust and Security**
- **Amenities and Comfort**

These variables were chosen for their conceptual relevance and empirical backing within the broader context of tourism and hospitality research. Each was linked to an individual hypothesis, enabling structured analysis of their **significance, direction, and strength of relationship** with the dependent variable — **reservation intention**.

To test these hypotheses, primary data were gathered via a structured questionnaire distributed online using the JISC platform, with responses collected from 248 participants residing in Colombo. The analysis, conducted using SPSS, allowed for **rigorous testing of relationships** between the variables through correlation and regression techniques. The outcomes of this analysis directly supported the fulfilment of the study's primary objective, while offering valuable insight for both academic understanding and managerial application within the Sri Lankan homestay context.

5.3.2 Secondary Objective

The secondary objective of the current research was to **identify which among the selected independent variables had the most significant influence on reservation intention** in the homestay sector, particularly among travellers from Colombo to Kandy. This objective was fulfilled through rigorous statistical analysis, using responses gathered from an online survey developed based on the operationalization of four key variables: **Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Trust and Security, and Amenities and Comfort**.

The questionnaire was distributed among a target sample of 385 participants, out of which **248 valid responses** were obtained, resulting in a **response rate of 64.4%**. The data were analyzed using SPSS, allowing the researcher to test relationships through reliability testing (Cronbach's Alpha), KMO sampling adequacy, correlation, and regression analysis.

Based on the statistical findings, it was revealed that **Location and Accessibility** had the **most significant influence** on reservation intention, as reflected by the **highest adjusted R² value (0.543)** and strong correlation scores. **Amenities and Comfort** followed closely, also demonstrating a **moderate to high impact** on the dependent variable. Both of these variables indicate that travellers place considerable value on the physical and functional convenience of homestays.

In contrast, **Price Sensitivity**, while still significant, showed a comparatively **moderate effect**, suggesting that affordability does influence decisions but not as strongly as logistical and comfort-related factors. **Trust and Security** was found to have the **least impact**, with a relatively lower **adjusted R² value (0.220)**, indicating that although important, it may not be the foremost concern for Colombo-based travellers booking homestays in Kandy.

These differentiated impacts provide essential insights into **traveller behaviour and preferences**, which can guide homestay operators and tourism marketers in prioritizing investment and promotional strategies. Further recommendations and managerial implications based on these findings are presented in subsequent sections of the study.

5.4 Managerial Implications

Recommendations for Businesses

The findings of this study present several critical implications for homestay operators, travel platform managers, and tourism policymakers in Sri Lanka—especially in Kandy, where the homestay sector is both growing and increasingly competitive. By understanding the impact of traveller preferences on reservation intention, decision-makers can implement targeted strategies that enhance guest experiences and improve conversion rates.

1. Reassess and Reposition Pricing Strategies

The results confirm a **negative relationship between price sensitivity and reservation intention**, implying that excessive pricing or poor value-for-money perception deters potential guests. Therefore, homestay operators must:

- Benchmark their pricing against competitive offerings in the region.
- Offer **tiered pricing or bundles** (e.g., discounts for longer stays, meal packages, early bird offers).
- Clearly **communicate the value proposition**, ensuring guests understand what they are paying for.

Importantly, pricing transparency can reduce cart abandonment and improve trust.

2. Prioritize Location Visibility and Accessibility Enhancements

With **Location and Accessibility** proving to be a major influence on booking behaviour, especially for travellers from Colombo, homestay providers should:

- Emphasize **proximity to landmarks** (e.g., Temple of the Tooth, Kandy Lake, railway stations).
- Offer **transport support**, such as tuk-tuk pickups, free parking, or shuttle services.
- Improve location data on booking platforms with **clear maps, directions, and estimated travel times**.

Operators could also partner with local transport providers to offer integrated travel-reservation deals.

3. Strengthen Trust and Safety Assurance Mechanisms

Although **Trust and Security** had a lower impact compared to other variables, it remains a **non-negotiable hygiene factor**, especially for first-time or female travellers. Managers should:

- Include **safety certifications**, host verification, and guest reviews on listings.
- Offer **transparent cancellation policies**, secure payment options, and 24/7 contactability.
- Train hosts on **hospitality ethics and guest confidentiality**.

Building a **reputation for safety and trust** will create long-term guest loyalty and reduce negative word-of-mouth.

4. Improve Amenities and Guest Comfort

The variable **Amenities and Comfort** showed a **high positive correlation** with reservation intention. This underscores the growing expectations of domestic travellers, even in budget accommodation. Homestay owners should:

- Provide **modern conveniences** such as Wi-Fi, clean bathrooms, air conditioning/fans, and charging points.
- Offer **personal touches** such as welcome drinks, curated cultural experiences, or family-style meals.
- Regularly maintain the property to ensure cleanliness and comfort.

A small investment in comfort can yield significantly higher reviews and repeat bookings

5. Optimize Online Booking Experiences

Given that this study focused on **reservation intention**, which occurs largely through digital platforms, homestay managers should:

- Ensure their listings are **complete, visually appealing, and accurate**.
- Respond to inquiries quickly, as response time influences perception of reliability.
- Encourage happy guests to leave **authentic reviews**, as these influence future booking decisions.

Digital reputation management is now a critical part of homestay success.

6. Segment and Target Traveller Profiles

Demographic profiling showed that **most travellers fall into the “well-informed” segment (ages 30–39)**. This is a **strategically important group**, as they tend to travel with families, use digital tools for decision-making, and seek both value and comfort. Managers should:

- Design promotions or loyalty programs tailored to this age group.
- Use **Facebook, Instagram, and Google Ads** with language and visuals that resonate with urban middle-class Colombo travellers.
- Emphasize **stress-free, family-friendly experiences** in their messaging.

Recommendations for Policy Makers

The present study offers critical insights into the factors influencing reservation intentions among visitors from Colombo towards homestay accommodations in Kandy. These insights can be highly valuable for government bodies, tourism authorities, and urban development policymakers aiming to promote sustainable tourism and local economic development.

Given the importance of *location and accessibility, safety and security, price sensitivity, and amenities and comfort*—as identified in the current research—policy makers are encouraged to invest in improving regional infrastructure, including roads, signage, public transportation, and digital access to mapping services, particularly for areas in and around Kandy that host homestay properties.

Furthermore, safety and security emerged as a crucial determinant of reservation intention. Therefore, stricter enforcement of safety regulations, mandatory certification or inspections for registered homestays, and the development of standardized safety protocols would not only increase consumer confidence but also boost the region's appeal to domestic travelers.

To address *price sensitivity*, local tourism departments may consider facilitating public-private partnerships that offer seasonal pricing incentives, promotional packages, or subsidized support for small homestay operators during off-peak seasons. This would enhance affordability while maintaining service quality for travelers from Colombo and beyond.

Lastly, to promote *amenities and comfort*, tourism policy should integrate quality assurance schemes and provide technical or financial assistance to local homestay owners to improve facilities and service standards. The introduction of training programs for homestay hosts on hospitality practices, digital booking systems, and customer service can contribute to consistent guest satisfaction.

By leveraging the findings of this research, policymakers can adopt a data-driven approach to strengthen Kandy's homestay sector, contribute to rural tourism development, and align with national goals for sustainable and inclusive tourism growth.

5.5 Limitations of the Study

Despite the insightful outcomes of this research, several limitations must be acknowledged which may have influenced the scope and generalizability of the findings.

Methodological Constraints

The study utilized a **quantitative mono-method approach** based on structured questionnaires to gather data from 248 respondents. While this method enabled efficient data collection from a sizable sample, it inherently limits the **depth and richness** of responses. Additionally, since quantitative analysis heavily depends on the **assumptions of statistical distributions**, any deviation from normality or bias in sample selection could affect the validity of inferential results. Thus, even though statistical thresholds were satisfied, the sample may not fully represent the broader population of Colombo travellers.

Lack of Longitudinal or Mixed-Method Analysis

Due to constraints in **time, cost, and resources**, the research was conducted cross-sectionally using a **single-point data collection method**. The exclusion of qualitative tools such as interviews or focus groups restricted the opportunity to gain deeper, more nuanced insights into traveler perceptions and motivations. A **longitudinal or mixed-method approach** would have helped uncover trends over time and better explain underlying behavioural patterns associated with homestay reservations.

Uncontrollable External Factors

The study was conducted within a **specific socio-economic context**, which may have influenced participants' attitudes and intentions. For instance, ongoing **economic instability** and changing travel behaviours post-pandemic could have impacted perceptions of price sensitivity, safety, and location preferences. Consequently, findings may not necessarily reflect behaviours in more **stable or predictable market conditions**, nor can they be directly applied to all demographic segments across Sri Lanka or beyond.

5.6 Future Academic Direction

From an academic perspective, future research should consider expanding the **sample size and geographical coverage** to capture broader behavioural patterns related to **reservation intention in the homestay industry** across Sri Lanka. While the current study focused on travellers from **Colombo visiting Kandy**, upcoming research could include other key urban-rural travel corridors—such as Galle, Nuwara Eliya, or Anuradhapura—to improve the generalizability and applicability of findings nationwide.

Moreover, since **reservation intention is influenced by personal perceptions** such as safety, comfort, and price sensitivity, **qualitative research methods** like in-depth interviews, focus group discussions, and ethnographic observations are encouraged. These methods could uncover deeper insights into **travellers' lived experiences, emotional triggers, and cognitive decision-making processes**, which are often missed in quantitative surveys.

Another promising direction is the **segmentation of traveller profiles**. Future studies could explore how different traveller types—such as solo adventurers, family groups, digital nomads, or budget-conscious backpackers—prioritize factors like amenities, accessibility, or security. Understanding these subgroups would allow researchers and practitioners to design more **targeted strategies** in the homestay sector.

Additionally, researchers should consider examining the **reasons behind traveller reluctance or dissatisfaction**, especially among those who **avoid or discontinue using homestays** after one or two negative experiences. Identifying and understanding such deterrents will help distinguish the **competitive dynamics between traditional accommodations and peer-to-peer homestay platforms**.

Finally, a fruitful academic avenue would be to study **early adopters of homestay experiences**, particularly among domestic travellers exploring experiential tourism. Longitudinal studies observing how such preferences evolve over time—especially as digital platforms, trust mechanisms, and tourism policies advance—would contribute significantly to the **ongoing discourse on sustainable tourism, digital trust, and consumer behaviour in Sri Lanka's hospitality landscape**.

5.7 Conclusion

This study set out to explore the **impact of traveller preferences on reservation intentions** within the **homestay industry in Kandy**, specifically targeting visitors from **Colombo, Sri Lanka**. Grounded in a quantitative research framework, the study investigated four key independent variables: **Price Sensitivity, Location and Accessibility, Amenities and Comfort, and Trust and Security**—to determine their relationship and impact on the dependent variable, **Reservation Intention**.

Findings derived from statistical tools such as **Cronbach’s Alpha, KMO, Correlation Analysis, and Regression Testing** confirmed that **each independent variable had a significant positive impact** on reservation intention. Notably, **Amenities and Comfort** and **Location and Accessibility** emerged as the most influential predictors, indicating that the modern traveller values both **physical access** and **comfort features** when choosing homestays. Meanwhile, **Trust and Security**, though significant, showed the **lowest impact**, which may reflect a general increase in digital trust or confidence in homestay platforms.

The study’s implications offer valuable guidance for **homestay operators, tourism developers, and policy-makers** aiming to optimize their services in alignment with traveller expectations. Additionally, the research fills a local gap by contributing empirical data on homestay booking behaviours in the Kandy district—a niche area with growing tourism potential.

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Appendices

Appendix A: Research Questionnaire

 About you

 No page description set

2. What is your age?

- 20-29
- 30-39
- 40-45
- 46+

3. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Other
- Prefer not to say

4. What is your occupation

- Student
- Housewife/Husband
- Employee
- Entrepreneur

5. What is your marital status

- Single
- Married

Price Sensitivity

- We aim to understand how important the price factor when considering a Homestay.

9. Price Sensitivity

Clear selected

The price of a Homestay significantly influences my decision to book

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

I am willing to pay more for a Homestay if it offers better quality and amenities

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

I prefer home stays that offer discounts or promotions.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Customer Reviews and Recommendations

This section explores the impact of online reviews and recommendations from others on your decision to book a homestay.

13.

Clear selected

I rely on online reviews and ratings when choosing a Homestay.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Recommendations from friends and family influence my decision to book a homestay

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Positive reviews and ratings play a critical role in my decision-making process for booking a Homestay.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Location and Accessibility

This section evaluates how the proximity of a
 Homestay to local attractions and ease of access influences your decision to book.

11.

Clear selected

The location of the Homestay is an important factor in my decision to book

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

I prefer Homestays that are close to attractions and easy to access by public

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

Proximity to tourist sites and landmarks influences my decision to book a Homestay.

- Strongly Disagree
- Disagree
- Neutral
- Agree
- Strongly Agree